

DIURETIC ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC PLANT EXTRACTS OF CLEOME GYNANDRA IN ALBINO WISTAR RATS

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 DIURETICS

Diuretics are the first-line treatment for eliminating extra fluid. They can be used alone or in conjunction with thiazides, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, loop diuretics, and thiazide like diuretics. Diuretics are used to increase the excretion of water and electrolytes in a variety of clinical settings. The British National Health Service lists sixteen distinct diuretics. formulary, with different ways of working. The majority of these substances affect renal tubular Naï reabsorption, which lowers the osmotic gradient and, consequently, the nephron's water reabsorption.^[1]

The indications, pharmacodynamics, and diuretic efficacy are unique to each type of diuretic because different diuretic drugs use different particular ion transport systems and the degree of Naï reabsorption changes throughout the nephron. Although they are less commonly used, mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists (MRAs) can be administered to counteract the negative effects of other diuretics, such as hypokalemia brought on by loop diuretics.

1.1.2 Renal anatomy and physiology

The glomerulus and formation of ultrafiltrate

An afferent arteriole supplies blood to each of the 800,000–1,000,000 nephrons that make up a typical kidney. Afferent arterioles create a Bowman's capsule contains a collection of

capillaries called the glomerulus.

The kidney's filtering unit is called the glomerulus. The kidneys of healthy people can produce a glomerular filtration rate (GFR) of up to 125 milliliters per minute of ultrafiltrate into the Bowman's capsule under typical circumstances.^[1]

1. The glomerular capillaries' fenestrated endothelium, the glomerular basement membrane, and visceral epithelial cells (podocytes)^[2] are all traversed by the generated ultrafiltrate.
2. The negatively charged glycocalyx restricts the filtration of negatively charged proteins like these, while these layers function as a semipermeable membrane permitting the flow of fluid, solutes, and proteins smaller than 70 kDa.^[2]

1.1.3 PROXIMAL CONVOLUTED TUBULE AND RESORPTION

Numerous adenosine triphosphate (ATP)-driven activities take place in the proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), where up to 70% of the ultrafiltrate is reabsorbed. The basolateral proximal tubule epithelial cells' Na⁺/K⁺ATPase pump is in charge of sodium ion reabsorption.

(Na⁺) together with water. Through ATP-dependent mechanisms, other solutes such as amino acids, bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), organic cations, anions, glucose, and phosphate (PO₄³⁻) are partially reabsorbed in the PCT.

1.1.4 LOOP OF HENLE AND FURTHER REABSORPTION

Through its counter-current multiplier system, the loop of Henle, which is in charge of further concentrating the urine, continues to absorb solutes and water. Up to 20–25% Here, water and filtered solutes are reabsorbed via the loop's thick ascending, thin descending, and thin ascending limbs. One The filtrate's osmolarity when entering the Henle loop is 300 mOsm L⁻¹.

Through aquaporin (AQP-1) channels, water diffuses out of the filtrate along a concentration gradient as it moves through the loop of Henle and into the interstitial fluid, raising the filtrate's osmolarity to about 1200 mOsm L⁻¹ when it reaches the inner medulla. Water cannot pass through the loop of Henle's thin ascending limb; only solutes may.

1.1.5 Distal convoluted tubule; further reabsorption and excretion

The distal convoluted tubule (DCT) is situated distal to the macula densa and is primarily responsible for fine tuning of ion homeostasis (Na⁺, K⁺, HCO₃⁻ and calcium ions [Ca²⁺]). Around 5-10% of the filtered Na⁺ is reabsorbed in the DCT, predominantly via the thiazide-sensitive Na⁺/Cl⁻ symporter, which reabsorbs Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions from tubular fluid.^[3] Aldosterone, produced in the adrenal cortex in response to low tubular flow at the macula densa, has some effect on Na⁺ reabsorption in the DCT (in exchange for K⁺).

1.1.6 Collecting duct fine tuning

Both principal cells and intercalated cells are found in the collecting duct (CD), and they are in charge of further concentration of the urine prior to its passage to the renal calyx.^[4] Principal cells also contain AQP-2 channels, which allow water reabsorption to occur under the influence of antidiuretic hormone (ADH, or vasopressin). Principal cells also contain epithelial Na⁺ channels (ENaC), which mediate Na⁺ entry into cells and increase the driving force for K⁺ secretion.

1.2 CAUSES OF DIURETICS

❖ Hypercalcemia

You will urinate more if your blood contains an excessive amount of calcium. It could develop into a medical emergency if you don't treat it. The most common reasons are parathyroid dysfunction and cancer.

❖ Abnormal Heart rate

Your heart may flutter if you have atrial fibrillation, but you may also need to urinate more frequently at night. An increased heart rate, or supraventricular tachycardia, can also cause increased urine production.

❖ High Altitude

At high altitude, you might urinate more for a brief period of time. You seem to be acclimating to the altitude, which is encouraging. When you are above 10,000 feet, this is probably what you will observe.

❖ Cold Temperature

As your body tries to warm up, your blood vessels constrict. This communicates with the kidneys to get rid of fluid.

❖ Diet

Alcohol, Caffeine and high-protein diet can raise the amount or how often you have to pee herbs and spices like parsley, dandelion, and ginger, may act as natural diuretics.

1.3. CLASSIFICATION OF DIURETICS

- Loop diuretics
- Thiazides
- Potassium sparing diuretics
- Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors
- Osmotic diuretics.

❖ LOOP DIURETICS

Individuals with salt and fluid overload conditions, such as cirrhosis with ascites, peripheral oedema, or pulmonary oedema, should take loop diuretics (such as bumetanide and furosemide); however, individuals with hypovolemia and cirrhosis). They need to get to the renal tubule's luminal surface in order to have an impact. Organic anion transporters (OATs) initially absorb them, after which they are secreted into the proximal tubule.

They have a diuretic effect, but they can also produce prostaglandins, which dilate blood vessels.

Before diuresis takes effect, this lowers cardiac preload, which relieves clinical dyspnea in patients with acute pulmonary oedema.

They are referred to as "high ceiling" diuretics since an increase in diuresis is accompanied with a gradually higher dosage. 5. Since loop diuretics are 96% protein bound, the glomerulus cannot filter them; instead, they reach their target in the PCT through the capillaries that are peritubular.^[5]

They work by blocking the Na⁺/K⁺/2Cl⁻ symport (NKCC2) in the thick ascending loop of Henle, which stops filtered Na⁺ from being reabsorbed and eventually causes Na⁺ and water loss. Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ reabsorption are influenced by the net positive electrical potential differential between the lumen and interstitium, which is caused by the NKCC2 symport.

These substances can therefore cause significant electrolyte abnormalities (such as

hypokalaemia, hyponatraemia, hypocalcaemia, hypomagnesaemia, and metabolic alkalosis) by blocking this symport. Ototoxicity, a dose-dependent consequence of blocking a Cl⁻ channel in the inner ear, is one of the additional negative consequences.^[5]

Specific effects of loop diuretics

- **Hypocalcemia and hypomagnesemia:** Blocking NKCC2 function leads to suppression of ROMK-mediated K⁺ recycling into the lumen, which leaves a decreased transepithelial voltage (with a less positive luminal charge).

This reduced luminal positivity reduces the driving force required for Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ reabsorption via the paracellular pathway, causing (see above) hypocalcemia and hypomagnesemia.

Despite the popular belief about hypomagnesemia caused by loop agents, a recent cohort study has concluded that thiazides but not loop diuretics are associated with the risk of hypomagnesemia.

- **Hyperuricemia:** Both loop and thiazide diuretics are anions that are secreted in exchange for urate molecules via the OATs leading to urate reabsorption and hence hyperuricemia. Thus these diuretics are associated with an increased risk of gouty attacks. A note, probenecid, a uricosuric agent used in gout, competes with urate to bind OATs leading to urate excretion.
- **Hypertriglyceridemia and Hypercholesterolemia:** Loop diuretics can increase the levels of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and triglycerides (TG) levels, but the mechanism for this remains unclear.
- **Hypochloremia** is associated with increased fractional excretion of Cl⁻ relative to that of Na⁺.
- **Ototoxicity** is a specific adverse effect of loop agents not shared by any other diuretic, and it manifests as sensory neural hearing loss, tinnitus, vertigo, or dizziness. Mechanism discussed further under toxicity.
- **Hypersensitivity reactions:** Furosemide can cause hypersensitivity reactions such as skin rashes or acute interstitial nephritis. Reports also exist of more severe anaphylactic

reactions.

- **Stevens-Johnson syndrome:** Loop diuretics have implications as a rare cause of Stevens-Johnson syndrome.
- Other less common adverse effects of loop diuretics include photosensitivity, nausea, and allergic interstitial nephritis.

Loop diuretics, especially furosemide and bumetanide, can displace bilirubin from albumin and cause hyperbilirubinemia leading to an increased risk of kernicterus in jaundiced neonates. Furosemide, rarely, can cause aplastic anemia and agranulocytosis.

❖ THIAZIDES

Essential hypertension is treated with thiazide diuretics. Protein-bound thiazides are similar to loop diuretics. They are transported to their site of action, which is situated on the DCT and the ascending loop of Henle, by the peritubular capillaries.

Here, they block the Naⁱ/Cl^e symport, which prevents the reabsorption of Na and Cl. Since this process accounts for around 5% of Naⁱ reabsorption, thiazide diuretics have a less diuretic impact than loop diuretics, but they still produce superior natriuresis. One Nevertheless, thiazides are beneficial for patients who are resistant to loop diuretics, as the DCT's Na⁺ transport capacity is increased by the hypertrophy of epithelial cells brought on by long-term loop diuretic medication.^[6]

Because of the Na⁺/K⁺ exchanger in the DCT, the increased Na⁺ load in the lumen also causes K⁺ and H⁺ ion loss. Using thiazide can result in Gout and hyperuricaemia due to decreased urate secretion. Hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and hypomagnesaemia are other negative consequences.

Thiazide-specific Effects

Electrolyte abnormalities are the most common adverse effects associated with chronic thiazide therapy in hypertension. They occur most commonly with longer-acting agents such as chlorthalidone and metolazone, but this is mitigated to an extent with a low-dose strategy.

- **Hypokalemia and metabolic alkalosis:** Thiazides can cause RAAS activation only via volume depletion (see above) as they act on NCC channels located distal to the macula

densa and do not influence salt-sensors located there.

Aldosterone from the RAAS pathway enhances the excretion of K^+ and H^+ in the tubules, as explained above. Also, thiazides cause decreased distal Ca^{2+} delivery, which stimulates ENaCs leading to increased K^+ secretion, thereby contributing to hypokalemia. They usually respond to K^+ replacement therapy very well.

- **Hyponatremia:** Even though loop diuretics suppresses a greater load of Na^+ reabsorption than other agents, hyponatremia most often results from thiazides because thiazides lead to reduced free-water clearance and they do not interfere with urine concentrating ability (countercurrent pathway) when compared to loop agents. Furthermore, increased water intake and increased vasopressin secretion contribute to dilutional hyponatremia.
- **Hypercalcemia/hypocalciuria** Volume depletion by thiazides causes enhanced Na^+ reabsorption in the PTs, which in turn stimulates increased passive Ca^{2+} reabsorption via paracellular pathway there, a proximal response.

As a distal response, inhibition of NCC channels by thiazides could play a role in enhancing Ca^{2+} reabsorption by modulating the activity of TRP vanilloid-5 channels.

- **Hypomagnesemia** also correlates with the chronic use of thiazides and is mediated through thiazide-mediated inhibition of NCC channels, which indirectly inhibits Mg^{2+} reabsorption via downregulating TRP melastatin-6 channels. Of note, a proton pump inhibitor also mediates hypomagnesemia via the same channels in both gastrointestinal (GI) and renal tubules.
- **Glucose intolerance:** Thiazide-induced hypokalemia in pancreatic interstitium hyperpolarizes the islet cells, thereby inhibiting calcium influx and thus decreasing the calcium-dependent release of insulin resulting in hyperglycemia.

Thiazides also cause an increase in the inflammatory response, abnormal lipid metabolism, RAAS activation, and oxidative stress, thus decreased insulin sensitivity that arises as a consequence is multifactorial. New-onset diabetes due to thiazides is also of concern in obese and hypertensive individuals.

- **Hyperuricemia:** The incidence of this adverse effect increases with the number of years using thiazides for hypertensive therapy.
- **Hypertriglyceridemia and Hypercholesterolemia:** Thiazides, while not affecting high-density lipoproteins, have been shown to increase LDL-C levels by 10%, total cholesterol by 4%, and TG levels by almost 15%. There is evidence on the dose-dependency of this side-effect and reduced occurrence with low-dose therapy.

❖ **POTTASIUM SPARING DIURETICS**

Aldosterone antagonists and medications that function independently of aldosterone are the two categories of potassium-sparing diuretics. Since spiro lactone and eplerenone are aldosterone antagonists, they prevent K^+ loss and Na^+ reabsorption.

These medications are released from the peritubular capillaries by blocking the DCT's aldosterone receptors. They are recommended for both primary hyperaldosteronism linked to bilateral adrenal hyperplasia and secondary hyperaldosteronism, in which the body produces more aldosterone in reaction to inadequate renal perfusion that results in the retention of salt and water (such as in liver cirrhosis or heart failure).^[6]

Spiro lactone's steroidal molecular nature makes it susceptible to gynecomastia and hirsutism.^[5,6] Triamterene and amiloride affect the DCT and CD without the help of aldosterone. The main purpose of these is to treat hypertension. In the glomerulus, they are freely filtered, preventing Na^+ entrance through ENaC in the DCT and CD. As a result, the lumen excretes less K^+ and H^+ .^[5,6] With their use, acidosis and hyperkalemia are not unusual.

Potassium-sparing Diuretic Specific Effects

More generalized and less common side-effects of K^+ -sparing agents include headache, fatigue, and GI disturbances like nausea, vomiting, constipation, diarrhea, anorexia, and abdominal pain.

ENaC Inhibitor Specific Effects

- **Hyperkalemia and hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis are** the most common side-effect of this class of diuretics due to their inhibition of ENaCs and, consequently, suppressed secretion of K^+ ions and H^+ ions from the ASDN.

This action results in hyperkalemia, and as with CAIs, the metabolic acidosis thus produced is hyperchloremic but via a different initial mechanism.

Hyperkalemia produced by these K⁺-sparing diuretics can lead to impaired PT ammonia generation and reduced collecting duct ammonia transport resulting in impaired ammonia excretion.

❖ **carbonic anhydrase inhibitors**

The PCT is where the carbonic anhydrase inhibitor acetazolamide works. The PCT's basolateral and luminal membranes contain the enzyme carbonic anhydrase, which catalyzes the HCO₃⁻ and H₂O ions are created when CO₂ and water undergo interconversion.

The PCT's Na⁺/H₂O exchanger is in charge of exchanging H₂O ions, which react with HCO₃⁻, for Na⁺ reabsorption. to create H₂CO₃. H₂CO₃ separates into H₂O and CO₂ when carbonic anhydrase is present. However, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, such as acetazolamide, decrease Na⁺ reabsorption by blocking carbonic anhydrase and lowering H₂O levels. Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis is caused by increased Cl⁻ reabsorption to maintain ionic equilibrium and alkaline urine due to impaired neutralization of luminal HCO₃⁻.

The distal nephron's elevated Na⁺ concentration causes an increase in K⁺ exchange, which in turn raises K⁺.^[6] Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors have a modest diuretic effect, which is partially due to the tubuloglomerular feedback mechanism being activated and the remaining nephron compensating for a larger Na⁺ load.^[6] Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors are not typically utilized for their diuretic effects because of their modest diuretic action.

They can be used to treat acute altitude sickness, certain types of metabolic alkalosis, and glaucoma (carbonic anhydrase helps create aqueous humor).

Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitor Specific Effects

- **Hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis:** Acetazolamide most commonly causes symptomatic metabolic acidosis. The majority of HCO₃⁻ ions are reabsorbed in the PT with the help of carbonic anhydrase enzyme, and inhibition of this enzyme by acetazolamide causes wastage of HCO₃⁻ ions in the urine (bicarbonaturia).

This activity leads to reduced serum HCO_3^- levels, and intracellular Cl^- ions are then released into the plasma to compensate for the loss of negative charge causing normal anion gap metabolic acidosis, aka hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis. Chronic use of acetazolamide is not warranted due to this side-effect.

- **Hypokalemia:** is due to increased distal delivery of Na^+ ions and their reabsorption in exchange for K^+ ions.
- **Fanconi syndrome:** Inhibition of HCO_3^- ions also cause type-2 proximal renal tubular acidosis, which can cause PT dysfunction leading to drug-induced Fanconi syndrome.

❖ Osmotic diuretics

Pharmacologically inert, osmotic diuretics like mannitol remain osmotically active within the tubular lumen active. By reducing water reabsorption, mannitol, which is readily filtered, creates an osmotic force that keeps water and Na^+ inside the tubule. Mannitol causes a greater degree of diuresis than natriuresis or kaliuresis, in contrast to other diuretic drugs.

As a result, it can cause hypernatraemia since it causes a proportionately greater loss of water than electrolytes. It is frequently employed as a rescue treatment to lower intracranial pressure and volume. In order to maximize GFR and maybe prevent acute kidney damage (AKI), it is still used in cardiac and vascular surgery. There is no benefit to this practice, according to recent data.^[7]

Osmotic Diuretic Specific Effects

- **Electrolyte abnormalities:** Though mannitol does not interfere with electrolyte reabsorptive mechanisms, it can cause inhibition of water transport, and this diminishes the ability of renal tubules to reabsorb Na^+ ions, which can cause hyponatremia.

Increased distal delivery of Na^+ ions can lead to K^+ loss as described above and thus hypokalemia. As it causes increased serum osmolality, mannitol causes a shift of water from the intracellular compartment to the plasma, leading to an increase in blood volume, which can further result in dilutional hyponatremia and hypokalemia.

- Mannitol-induced overt expansion of extracellular fluid volume can precipitate pulmonary edema in HF patients due to hypervolemia.

With frequent use, mannitol sometimes can worsen cerebral edema as it can cross the already damaged blood-brain barrier (as in intracranial hemorrhage) and draws water into the brain.

Mannitol less commonly can form precipitates at low temperatures, which can cause vascular and end-organ damage.

1.4. Relationship between diuretic therapy and renal function

Diuretic use in chronic kidney disease and heart failure

"Diuretic resistance" frequently develops in the context of heart failure or chronic kidney disease (CKD), necessitating higher dosages of diuretics to get the same result. There are a number of causes for this behavior. Patients with CKD and heart failure have reduced diuretic delivery to the tubule, which results in less diuretic production and lower concentration at the tubular lumen's sites of action. Less filtered plasma and Na^+ are present as GFR declines, which restricts the maximum diuretic action.

For instance, in individuals with a GFR of approximately $15 \text{ ml min}^{-1} 1.73 \text{ m}^2$, only around 10–20% of the furosemide that would be eliminated in a patient with normal renal function is secreted. To ensure that the tubule receives sufficient quantities, a higher dosage of the diuretic must be administered.^[8]

Furthermore, metabolic acidosis (such as in patients with CKD and AKI) impairs the secretion of loop diuretics into the tubule lumen via OATs, necessitating higher dosages. When taking a diuretic repeatedly, "tolerance" may develop. Target transporters are elevated by long-term use of loop and thiazide diuretics; loop diuretic resistance arises from distal nephron segment hypertrophy and increased Na^+ reabsorption with increased distal tubule exposure. By blocking these distal nephron sites with a thiazide diuretic, this can be avoided.

The effects of loop diuretics wear off quickly, and their half-lives are away after several hours. "Post-diuretic NaCl retention" is the result of the kidney compensating by holding onto the water and salt that have been lost. As a result, it is now advised that critically ill patients take loop diuretics at least twice daily.^[9]

1.5 Use of diuretics in intensive care units loop Diuretic

Furosemide is often used as the initial step in this procedure. A The usual initial dosage of furosemide intravenously is 40–80 mg or 1 mg kg^{-1} , with higher dosages based on response. It is advised that the dose be increased and administered again until the necessary clinical

effects are obtained if there is little to no response within 1–2 hours after an intravenous bolus.^[9] In order to treat the kidney's post-diuretic salt-avid state, furosemide is usually administered twice to four times per day in the intensive care unit (ICU), but it can also be administered continuously. Bolus dosage has the potential advantage of reaching a greater peak dose in the renal tubular system. A daily intake of no more than 1.5 g is advised.

Usually, the increased K⁺ concentration dilutes the increased urine volume. and because more water is lost than Na, hypokalaemia and hypernatraemia accompany therapy. To reduce serum electrolyte abnormalities, furosemide is frequently coupled with other diuretics as indapamide or spiro lactone.

Aldosterone Antagonist

In return for K⁺, Na⁺ is reabsorbed as the filtrate gets to the DCT. An aldosterone antagonist like spironolactone or the diuretic amiloride can be used to reverse these effects. as a diuretic that spares K⁺. Higher serum K⁺ concentrations and increased urine Na⁺ loss are the results of both. When treating oedema, 100–400 mg of spiro lactone are administered orally per day. The recommended dosage for amiloride is 10 mg o.d. up to a maximum of 20 mg day⁻¹. For patients without gastrointestinal uptake, there is regrettably no intravenous substitute.

Thiazide Diuretics

Increased loss of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ in the urine is another effect of thiazide diuretics on the DCT. Thiazide diuretics include bendroflumethiazide and hydrochlorothiazide. Oedema can be treated with bendroflumethiazide 5–10 mg taken orally o.d., however healthy people have a half-life. of just 2e5 h. Patients with chronic kidney disease frequently take metolazone, a thiazide-like diuretic with strong diuretic effects.

Metolazone starting oral dosages of 2.5 mg frequently cause strong diuretic effects. Another option is indapamide 2.5 mg o.d., which has a 93% oral bioavailability and a 15–25 hour half-life in healthy individuals. Hyponatraemia results from thiazides' excessive salt and chloride loss in the urine.

Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors

Na⁺ and HCO₃⁻ ions remain in the renal tubule because acetazolamide increases H⁺ excretion. Urine becomes alkaline as a result. with elevated bicarbonate and sodium levels. The exchange and loss of potassium in the urine will also result from the delivery of this salt

to the collecting tubule.

A typical anion gap metabolic acidosis results from the retention of chloride in exchange for the HCO₃^e. While it might not always facilitate the transition off of mechanical ventilation, this side effect may be helpful in individuals with chronic hypercapnia and persistent metabolic alkalosis. 22 The typical dosage is divided into 250–1000 mg daily.^[10]

1.6. Diuretics are frequently used for critically ill patients in the following circumstances when fluid buildup impairs organ function when ongoing fluid administration is required despite the danger of fluid buildup; and as an adjuvant treatment for hypertension.

Less frequent indications include:

- (i) The requirement for forced diuresis to get rid of harmful compounds or treat tumor lysis syndrome, and osmotherapy to control increased intracerebral pressure. Oliguria by itself is not a sign.

The objective is to reduce intravascular hydrostatic pressure, interstitial oedema, and compartmental pressures while increasing urine production. measurements used as a stand-in for raised Increased central venous pressure (CVP), pulmonary capillary wedge pressure (PCWP), natriuretic peptides, and imaging indicators of oedema are examples of intravascular hydrostatic pressure.

Transpulmonary thermodilution, which measures extravascular lung water when it is accessible, also shows a correlation with pulmonary oedema.

How to keep an eye on diuretics

Monitoring diuretic therapy involves assessment of the balance between effectiveness (i.e. diuresis, resolution of fluid accumulation) and safety. Indicators of effective fluid removal and decongestion include clinical signs (e.g. improved respiratory status), decreasing levels of natriuretic peptides, improved organ function [i.e. improved serum creatinine (SCr), improved oxygenation], resolution of congestion on imaging and decrease in CVP or PCWP.

Under the moniker VexuS, doppler-based scores have drawn attention as a means of assessing organ venous congestion. Although this method works well, it is not It takes training to obtain enough Doppler signals, but it is always possible.

What happens if individuals respond well to diuretics but have insufficient urine production or are unable to reach the recommended fluid balance?

Hypovolemia, refractory venous congestion, insufficient concentrations at sites of action (such as hemodynamic instability, inadequate dosage), and inadequate renal function all reduce the effectiveness of diuretics.

Higher dosages of diuretics may be necessary for patients with compromised kidney function, such as those with acute kidney injury (AKI) or chronic kidney disease (CKD). Urine production that is insufficient or decreasing could indicate that intravascular hypovolemia has set in or that the dosage is too low. Both ought to take the lead.

A precise assessment of fluid status is required to inform choices and distinguish between intravascular hypovolemia and congestion of the veins. Collapsible inferior vena cava and hyperkinetic motions (i.e., kissing heart on cardiac ultrasound) are indicators of volume depletion on ultrasonography.

Patients who exhibit symptoms of hypoperfusion (such as rising plasma lactate, cold extremities, mottled skin, or extended capillary refill time) should stop taking diuretics in response to indicators of fluid responsiveness, low CVP, or hemoconcentration (i.e., rising plasma protein concentration).

Treatment escalation (i.e., dose and/or frequency) is the first step, followed by diuretic combination therapy and fluid intake reduction if fluid buildup and congestion continue after diuretic administration or if the recommended fluid balance cannot be reached.

Interestingly, intravascular hypovolemia and renal congestion can sometimes occur simultaneously, as in the case of syndrome of the intraabdominal compartment. The goal in this case is to correct the underlying disease and do hemodynamic resuscitation.

Can serum creatinine increase?

Although diuretics themselves are not nephrotoxic, significant fluid loss might result in a drop in glomerular filtration and renal perfusion. Hemoconcentration and effective fluid depletion are indicated by a modest increase in SCr, often known as "pseudo-worsening of renal function." In heart failure, decongestion is linked to better clinical results and frequently outweighs the dangers of SCr alterations.

On the other hand, ongoing congestion is linked to worse outcomes when renal function deteriorates. Decongestion should therefore be given first priority.

When accessible, tubular damage biomarkers (such as neutrophil gelatinase associated lipocalin, cell cycle arrest markers, and renal injury molecule-1) might assist distinguish between actual kidney damage and the anticipated creatinine variations brought on by decongestion.

What negative consequences are expected?

- Hypokalemia,
- Hypermnatremia,
- Hypomagnesemia,
- Hypophosphatemia,
- Hypocalcemia, and
- Metabolic alkalosis are all possible side effects of loop diuretics.

1.7 PHARMACOKINETICS OF DIURETICS:

The key clinical and pharmacokinetic aspects of each subclass of diuretics. The most important adverse effects are derangements in electrolytes, particularly serum potassium, which may be lowered by thiazides and loop diuretics and elevated by aldosterone antagonists.

The longer duration of action of chlorthalidone, torasemide, and azosemide may be partly responsible for their greater efficacy in reducing CVEs relative to their alternatives (see below).

It should be noted that the diuretic-induced reduction in salt and water activates hormonal systems such as vasopressin, the renin–angiotensin–aldosterone system, and the sympathetic nervous system.

This may lead to a relatively flat dose–BP response curve in patients with hypertension. However, in the case of chlorthalidone, these effects can be eradicated by the coadministration of spironolactone.

1.8 MECHANISM OF ACTION OF DIURETICS

Diuretics exert their effects by targeting different segments of the nephron, altering the sodium, water, and electrolyte balance to promote diuresis. Each class of diuretics has a distinct mechanism of action.

Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibitors

Acetazolamide and metazolamide are examples of carbonic anhydrase inhibitors that block the enzyme by acting on the proximal convoluted tubule. As a result, bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and sodium (Na^+) are decreased. $(-)$ reabsorption, which causes these ions and water to be excreted in greater amounts through the urine. The body lowers CO_2 levels to make up for metabolic acidosis brought on by bicarbonate loss, which results in respiratory alkalosis through hyperventilation.

Potassium loss as a result of a changed electrolyte balance is a noteworthy adverse consequence of this class. Carbonic anhydrase inhibitors also help lower blood pressure, intracranial pressure, and intraocular pressure by decreasing blood volume.^[11,12]

Loop diuretics

By blocking the $\text{Na}^+/\text{K}^+/\text{2Cl}^-$ cotransporter, loop diuretics such as furosemide, bumetanide, ethacrynic acid, indacrinone, and torasemide act on the ascending limb of the Henle loop, preventing sodium reabsorption and encouraging water excretion.

These are the strongest diuretics, and they work even when GFR is low.^[11] But soon after starting treatment, acute tolerance may set up, resulting in the "braking phenomenon," in which compensatory mechanisms cause sodium retention.^[11,12]

In order to accomplish a sequential nephron blockage, loop diuretics can be combined with thiazide-related diuretics, or the dosage, frequency, or dietary sodium intake can be changed. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that acetazolamide and loop diuretics work together to reduce sodium reabsorption in the proximal tubule, hence overcoming diuretic resistance.^[12]

Thiazide and thiazide like diuretics

The distal convoluted tubule is the primary site of action for thiazide diuretics, including hydrochlorothiazide, clopamide, chlorthalidone, indapamide, and xipamide. Here, they block sodium reabsorption, increasing the excretion of water and sodium.^[13]

Associated with thiazide Despite having a somewhat different chemical structure, diuretics and thiazides work similarly. Because they have a moderate diuretic efficacy and cause fewer metabolic and electrolyte disruptions than loop diuretics, these medications are frequently used to treat hypertension and edema.^[14]

Potassium sparing diuretics

Potassium-sparing diuretics work by blocking potassium excretion and blocking sodium reabsorption in the distal convoluted tubule and collecting ducts. They work through two methods:

- By blocking aldosterone receptors, aldosterone antagonists (spironolactone, canrenone, canrenoic acid, and eplerenone) lessen potassium loss and salt retention.
- Triamterene and amiloride, two sodium channel blockers, directly block sodium channels in the distal tubule, lowering sodium reabsorption and maintaining potassium.^[14]

These medications are very helpful for hyperaldosteronism and heart failure, which are disorders caused by an excess of aldosterone. Triamterene and amiloride are frequently used to prevent potassium loss brought on by other diuretics. Furthermore, spironolactone possesses anti-androgenic qualities, which makes it beneficial for treating ailments like hirsutism.^[15]

Osmotic Diuretics

By establishing an osmotic gradient, mannitol and sorbitol mainly block water reabsorption in the proximal tubule. Water is drawn from tissues into the bloodstream and eventually into the urine by mannitol, which raises the serum osmolarity. Mannitol is very useful in lowering intracranial pressure and cerebral edema since it does not pass through the blood–brain barrier.^[16] Acute RF, glaucoma crises, and hypovolemic disorders are also treated with osmotic diuretics.

Vasopressin receptor antagonist

Increased water excretion without appreciable sodium loss results from the selective antagonization of vasopressin receptors by conivaptan and tolvaptan. Conivaptan works non-selectively on vasopressin receptors and is exclusively administered intravenously, unlike tolvaptan, an is a selective antagonist of the vasopressin V2 receptor that is taken orally.

The syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone secretion (SIADH) and hyponatremia are the main conditions for which these medications are prescribed.^[17]

Inhibitors of Sodium-Glucose Cotransporter 2 (SGLT2)

A class of oral antidiabetic medications known as SGLT2 inhibitors increases the excretion of sodium and glucose by blocking SGLT2 receptors in the proximal tubule. This lowers the volume of extracellular fluid by an osmotic diuretic action. The kidneys gradually adjust to restore fluid balance, therefore this diuretic impact is only temporary.^[18,19]

Angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) Inhibitors

ACE inhibitors reduce angiotensin II-mediated salt retention, which has moderate natriuretic and diuretic effects, despite their primary usage as antihypertensive medications. Despite helping to reduce blood pressure, this side effect is insufficiently strong for main treatment with diuretics. ACE inhibitors are frequently prescribed by clinicians for chronic renal disease, heart failure, and hypertension. It is crucial to regularly check electrolyte levels and renal function.^[20]

Reduced aldosterone secretion can result in hyperkalemia, especially in individuals with renal impairment or those on medications that retain potassium, such as aliskiren, aldosterone antagonists, or sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim. Potassium levels and renal function need to be regularly observed.

Elevated levels of bilirubin and creatinine may result from a modest decrease in GFR at the start of treatment. In individuals with heart failure or bilateral renal artery stenosis, where inadequate renal perfusion further lowers the GFR, this effect is more noticeable. Hypotension is more prevalent in patients who have hypovolemia or high baseline renin levels. Those who have volume or salt deprivation are recommended to exercise caution.

Diuretics should be stopped two to three days prior to starting ACE inhibitor medication. Treatment should start with the lowest dose of an ACE inhibitor if stopping is not feasible.^[20,21]

The Diuretic Effect of Alcohol

Alcoholic drinks with more than 13.5% alcohol can temporarily block the antidiuretic hormone (ADH), encouraging water excretion without causing electrolyte imbalances loss.

However, in dehydrated individuals, alcohol does not exhibit diuretic effects due to compensatory mechanisms that prevent further fluid loss.^[22]

1.9 INDICATIONS OF DIURETICS

The TRANSFORM-HF research and the New York Heart Association's (NYHA) and the European Society of Cardiology's (ESC) guidelines state that cardiogenic pulmonary edema is a condition that calls for immediate diuretic treatment.

The well-known loop diuretics are the best option for HF symptoms due to their quick onset and effectiveness; furosemide is the most often utilized medication. These diuretics are started at low dosages and then gradually increased in accordance with body weight measurements and diuresis monitoring.^[23,24,25]

The inclusion of thiazide diuretics, such as metolazone or hydrochlorothiazide, increases their diuretic action and further reduces symptoms when loop diuretics alone are not enough for the treatment of heart failure.^[26] Aldosterone antagonists have also been demonstrated to lower mortality and morbidity in patients with a left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) of less than 35% and progressive systolic HF.^[27]

The first-line treatment for ascites in decompensated liver cirrhosis also involves diuretics and dietary salt limits. Because of its antiandrogenic qualities and targeted impact on the underlying pathology, spironolactone is the recommended treatment in this situation.

If spironolactone is not enough on its own, a loop diuretic may be added, or it may be incorporated into a combination treatment right away. In both HF and liver cirrhosis, renal dysfunction exacerbates fluid retention through the activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS).^[28,29]

A major side effect of RF and other nephropathies is hyperhydration, which is linked to a higher death rate.

Although loop diuretics are the recommended first line of treatment, extrarenal replacement therapy may be necessary in advanced CKD with resistant hyperhydration. be required for long-term administration.

Diuretic therapy is crucial in nephrotic syndrome, which is defined by proteinuria over 3.5 g/24 hours, hypoalbuminemia resulting in decreased oncotic pressure and subsequent fluid extravasation, and hyperlipidemia. In individuals with hypoalbuminemia and renal failure, the combination of albumin with furosemide or furosemide and triamterene has shown

promise.^[30,31]

Among the first-line therapies for hypertension are thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics. According to a Cochrane research and the guidelines of the European Society of Hypertension (ESH), a loop diuretic should be used when the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) is between 30 and 45 mL/min. If the eGFR falls below 30 milliliters per minute, chlorthalidone might be taken in conjunction with a loop diuretic, as advised by the ESH 2024 guidelines and the American College of Cardiology (ACC).^[32,33]

Comparing low-dose, long-acting chlorthalidone to other antihypertensive drugs, it has been shown to significantly lower the risk of cardiovascular events. For hypertensive patients with diabetes, indapamide is a safer option because it does not affect glucose or lipid metabolism and has less metabolic adverse effects than chlorthalidone.

Additionally, thiazide diuretics directly dilate blood vessels, which lowers blood pressure over the long run. When CKD and hypertension coexist, loop diuretics are still the recommended option, particularly if the GFR is less than 30 mL/min. Patients with hypertension who have potassium (K⁺) or magnesium deficiency are also treated with potassium-sparing diuretics. deficits in (Mg²⁺).^[34]

Since thiazide diuretics encourage calcium reabsorption, they may be helpful for patients with nephrolithiasis and hypercalciuria. Loop diuretics, such as furosemide, on the other hand, raise calciuria, which may be advantageous for people who exhibit symptoms of hypercalciuria.

Thiazide diuretics paradoxically aid in diabetic insipidus, a disorder characterized by polyuria and the production of diluted urine with a low solute content, by encouraging sodium (Na⁺) excretion in the proximal tubules, which lowers the kidneys' maximum diluting ability.

By encouraging the excretion of bicarbonate, acetazolamide, a sulfonamide with no antibacterial properties, causes metabolic acidosis. It prevents high altitude sickness by preventing hypoxia-induced respiratory alkalosis. When alternative therapies are not appropriate, acetazolamide is frequently used to treat open-angle glaucoma in the short term since it is also effective at lowering intraocular pressure. It has also been used to treat epilepsy because it can lessen the severity and length of seizures.^[35,36]

Osmotic diuretics, such mannitol, are inappropriate for disorders linked to sodium retention since they mainly increase water excretion rather than salt elimination. Mannitol, however, efficiently lowers intracranial pressure in less than an hour, yet There could be a brief, initial rise in pressure. In cases of acute kidney injury (AKI), it is also used to promote diuresis and aid in the elimination of harmful metabolic compounds.^[37]

Diuretics are also used to increase the amount of urine produced per unit of time in order to eliminate toxins by forced diuresis. When a patient is poisoned by medications like salicylates, phenobarbital, or lithium, clinical pharmacists use loop diuretics and urine alkalization.^[37]

1.9 HOW TO ADMINISTER DIURETICS

Although diuretics are usually taken orally, they are sometimes given intravenously in hospital settings or emergency situations where maximum strength is required, such as in advanced heart failure (HF), acute pulmonary edema, cerebral edema, or barbiturate poisoning. In this situations, continuous infusion is better than bolus shots. To prevent and reduce side effects, the patient's comorbidities should be taken into account while selecting the diuretic, dosage, and administration method.^[38,39]

Loop diuretics

Loop diuretics are quickly absorbed and reach their maximal levels in 30 to 2 hours. Bumetanide and torasemide have oral bioavailabilities of above 80%, while furosemide has the lowest bioavailability at 61%. These diuretics can be found in both intravenously and orally. While bumetanide and torasemide are processed by the liver, furosemide is mostly eliminated unaltered in urine (66%) or through kidney metabolism. Torasemide can be used once daily because it has the greatest half-life (3–4 hours) and the longest duration of action (12 hours). Food consumption has little effect on torasemide absorption, in contrast to furosemide and bumetanide.^[40]

Because shorter-acting loop diuretics might cause post-diuretic sodium retention after their effects wear off, the frequency of dosage is very important. They are typically administered twice day as a result.

Diuretics that Thiazide

When used orally, thiazide diuretics with a sulfonamide composition are readily absorbed

from the gastrointestinal (GI) tract. Their bioavailabilities vary from 50% to 95%; the bioavailabilities of hydrochlorothiazide and chlorthalidone are 71% and 65%, respectively. Oral hydrochlorothiazide dosages range from 25 to 100 mg, and it is recommended to take the medication in the morning or at midday rather than at night.^[41]

With a 93% bioavailability, indapamide is a thiazide-like diuretic that is usually recommended for the treatment of essential hypertension at a dosage of 2.5 mg per day (or 1.5 mg per day in sustained-release form). The suggested daily dosage for edematous situations is 2.5–5 mg.^[42,43]

Potassium sparing diuretics

Amiloride is not metabolized and is expelled unaltered, with roughly half going through the pee and the other half through the feces. On the other hand, the liver converts triamterene into active metabolites. Because it doesn't have hepatic metabolism.

For people with liver problems, amiloride is recommended. However, due to the possibility of drug buildup and hyperkalemia, it should be avoided in situations of renal failure. Triamterene needs to be administered twice day, whereas amiloride can be taken once daily.

The oral bioavailability of both medications is roughly 50%.^[45] Although eplerenone is metabolized in the liver, no active metabolites are produced. It binds to albumin at a level of about 50% in serum proteins. About 32% of the medication is removed through feces, and the remaining 67% is expelled by urine.^[46]

Eplerenone has an oral bioavailability of approximately 69% and undergoes hepatic metabolism without forming active metabolites. It binds to serum albumin at about 50%, with around 67% of the drug excreted in the urine and 32% eliminated via the feces. Food does not interfere with its absorption; in fact, taking eplerenone with food may help reduce gastric irritation and associated adverse effects.^[47,48] Eplerenone is more selective than spironolactone, but it is also a weaker mineralocorticoid receptor antagonist and has a shorter half-life.

Consequently, eplerenone must be administered twice daily to exert its full effect.^[49] A newer class of mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists, which includes finerenone and hexaxenone, is now available, but these drugs are not used as diuretics.

For instance, finerenone is authorized to lower IR progression, heart failure, myocardial infarctions, and cardiovascular mortality in individuals with type 2 diabetes and chronic kidney disease (CKD), but not high blood pressure. Notably, even though it is In Japan, hexaxerone is authorized for the treatment of hypertension despite carrying a slight but noteworthy risk of hyperkalemia.^[50]

Carbonic anhydrase inhibitor and osmotic diuretics

Acetazolamide, which is rarely used in clinical practice, is well absorbed by the GI tract, is not metabolized, and has a plasma protein binding level of 93%. It has an onset of action within 1 to 1.5 h, with nearly 100% oral bioavailability and a plasma half-life of 13 h. It should be taken twice daily.

Approximately 90% of acetazolamide is excreted unchanged in the urine through tubular secretion.

As a result, it is ineffective in patients with renal insufficiency. Mannitol is poorly absorbed orally, and is therefore administered only via a slow i.v. infusion at 1–1.5 g/kg/day. Effective osmotic diuresis requires 0.5–2 L of 10% mannitol. With no tubular reabsorption, glomerular filtration eliminates about 90% of mannitol unaltered.^[51]

Mannitol should be used carefully because it can exacerbate cerebral edema. every six to eight hours. Overdosing could cause hyperperfusion syndrome by overtaxing the heart and circulatory system.^[52,53]

1.10 SIDE EFFECT OF DIURETICS

The most common adverse effect of diuretics is mild hypovolemia, which can lead to transient dehydration and increased thirst. In cases of prolonged diuretic therapy, severe hypovolemia may occur, resulting in hypotension, dizziness, and syncope.

The general side effects associated with diuretic use include

- headaches,
- frequent urination,
- restlessness,
- weakness,
- fatigue, and

- lethargy.
- Gastrointestinal disturbances—such as
 - nausea,
 - vomiting,
 - constipation,
 - diarrhea,
- anorexia, and
- abdominal pain—are more frequently observed with loop diuretics than with other classes of diuretics.^[54,55]

Any diuretic medication might cause electrolyte abnormalities. Most diuretics cause hypokalemia (serum potassium < 3.5 mmol/L), with the exception of those that operate on the convoluted nephron collecting tubule, which can result in hyperkalemia (serum potassium < 3.5 mmol/L). potassium levels above 5.5 mmol/L.

Because of their interconnected reabsorption pathways in the renal tubules, acid-base disturbances frequently accompany electrolyte abnormalities^[56,57] Aldosterone receptor antagonist are specifically linked to metabolic acidosis and hyperkalemia. (ARAs), include eplerenone, spironolactone, amiloride, and triamterene. Interestingly, it has been proposed that the risk of hyperkalemia can be decreased by combining sodium–glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors with mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists (MRAs).^[58]

Additionally, diuretics may cause metabolic abnormalities that impact lipid, uric acid, and serum glucose levels. Impotence, hyperglycemia, skin responses, thrombocytopenia, aplastic anemia, agranulocytosis, hemolytic anemia, muscle cramps, and myalgia are less frequent adverse effects.

Since loop diuretics have the largest diuretic impact, side effects are typically dose-dependent and most noticeable.

- Hyponatremia,
- Hypokalemia,
- Metabolic alkalosis,
- Hypocalcemia,
- Hypomagnesemia,

- Hyperuricemia,
- Hyperglycemia,
- And increases in creatinine and blood urea nitrogen (BUN) are a few examples of these abnormalities.

Nevertheless, these adverse effects have been significantly decreased by regulated formulations with lower dosages, especially with thiazide diuretics.^[59] Sodium is necessary for controlling the volume and concentration of extracellular fluid, preserving maintaining acid-base homeostasis, promoting transmembrane transport, maintaining appropriate neuromuscular excitability, and maintaining osmotic balance.

The body needs between 150 and 250 mEq of sodium per day, or 9 to 15 g of NaCl, and the main source of this is through eating. Hormones like aldosterone and deoxycorticosterone promote the active absorption of sodium in the intestines. Sweat, digestive secretions, and urine excretion are the ways that salt is eliminated.^[60]

The central nervous system (CNS) is the primary organ affected by hyponatremia symptoms, particularly when sodium levels drop sharply and quickly. Typically, neurological symptoms do not appear until serum sodium levels drop to 120–125 mEq/L.

Below 115 mEq/L may cause neurological malfunction and a coma. Children, premenopausal women, mental patients with polydipsia, and the elderly, especially those on thiazide diuretics or experiencing hypoxia, are among the high-risk patients. Increased intracranial pressure results from intracellular water inflow when salt levels fall.^[61]

Thiazide diuretics, steroidal MRAs, and finerenone can all cause hyponatremia. A 2024 study found that, in adults aged 40 and older, thiazide diuretic were associated with a significantly higher risk of hyponatremia over a two-year period compared to non-thiazide antihypertensive agents, with the highest risk occurring within the first 60 days of treatment.^[62]

The use of thiazide diuretics alongside spironolactone or loop diuretics more than doubles the risk of hospitalization due to hyponatremia.^[63]

Hypomagnesemia is a common complication of both loop and thiazide diuretics.^[64] Loop diuretics, while useful in the management of severe hypercalcemia, require careful volume

management to avoid dehydration. Initial hypercalcemia treatment involves saline replenishment, followed by loop diuretics to promote calciuresis.

Loop diuretics' natriuretic and calciuretic effects are still advantageous in certain situations, despite some research casting doubt on their exact function in the treatment of hypercalcemia.^[65,66]

When a loop diuretic is taken at a dose that is appropriate for renal function, diuretic resistance occurs when enough sodium excretion is not achieved. Although they may resemble diuretic resistance, conditions like edematous states (such as those linked to dihydropyridine calcium channel blockers, hypothyroidism, lymphedema, or venous stasis) usually do not improve with diuretic medication.

As shown in an experimental investigation where rats implanted with infusion pumps giving a continuous furosemide dose developed resistance over time, long-term treatment of loop diuretics can result in diuretic resistance.^[67]

When diuretic resistance occurs, maximizing To improve the pharmacokinetic efficacy, treatment options include doubling the dosage, using a continuous intravenous infusion rather than a bolus injection, or switching to a more bioavailable loop diuretic such torsemide or bumetanide. For hypomagnesemia, amiloride may be used as an adjuvant treatment.

Amiloride decreased urinary magnesium losses in a dose-dependent way in rodents given furosemide, according to studies.^[67] This was most likely due to direct renal effects.

Ototoxicity, which shows up as sensorineural hearing loss or tinnitus, can be brought on by loop diuretics. When loop diuretics are taken with aminoglycoside antibiotics, this impact is more noticeable; nonetheless, the symptoms usually go away when the medicine is stopped.^[68]

Before starting high-dose boluses or rapid infusions, hearing tests should be performed to reduce the risk and provide a personalized evaluation of the effect of loop diuretics on auditory function. During extended treatment, periodic evaluation of hearing function is also advised. To avoid irreversible aural impairment, switching to an other diuretic treatment should be considered if side effects occur.

Due to increased serum drug concentrations, ototoxicity is most commonly seen when furosemide is administered in high doses as a bolus to patients with AKI. Ethacrynic acid is the most ototoxic of the loop diuretics.

To improve the pharmacokinetic efficacy, treatment options include doubling the dosage, using a continuous intravenous infusion rather than a bolus injection, or switching to a more bioavailable loop diuretic such as torsemide or bumetanide. For hypomagnesemia, amiloride may be used as an adjuvant treatment. Amiloride decreased urinary magnesium losses in a dose-dependent way in rodents given furosemide, according to studies.

This was most likely due to direct renal effects of furosemide in AKI because of high levels of the medication in the blood.

Among loop diuretics, ethacrynic acid is the most ototoxic. Several diuretics, including hydrochlorothiazide, furosemide, spironolactone, and triamterene, have been associated with hepatotoxicity. In elderly patients, diuretic-induced renal impairment can be exacerbated by a reduced thirst sensitivity, leading to excessive dehydration.

Diuretics may also increase the risk of AKI under conditions where renal perfusion is compromised, such as congestive heart failure, liver cirrhosis, and nephrotic syndrome. Additionally, higher diuretic doses are linked to glomerular basement membrane damage, tubular epithelial cell degeneration, and an increased susceptibility to nephrotoxicity, particularly when combined with other nephrotoxic drugs. As a result, the use of diuretics in conjunction with nephrotoxic agents should be carefully evaluated or avoided when possible.^[69,70]

1.11 MANAGEMENT OF DIURETIC THERAPY

Diuretic therapy necessitates the close monitoring of extracellular fluid volume, urine output, plasma and urine electrolyte levels, body weight, serum glucose, and blood pressure. Regular evaluations are especially important for patients with cardiovascular, hepatic, renal, or metabolic conditions, as well as for the elderly. Hypovolemia caused by diuretics can result in extrarenal azotemia, highlighting the need to monitor the BUN and creatinine levels closely.^[71]

Ototoxicity is a known risk associated with loop diuretics, and appropriate precautions are essential. Baseline hearing assessments are recommended, particularly when high doses,

bolus injections, or rapid infusions are planned. These assessments enable tailored monitoring during the course of therapy and aid in assessing the possible effects of loop diuretics on auditory function.^[72,73]

The sequential, regular observation of auditory function is also suggested when using loop diuretics. To reduce further risk and maintain hearing function, switching to an alternate diuretic regimen should be taken into consideration if symptoms of ototoxicity or other negative effects appear.^[74,75]

Since abrupt changes in the fluid balance between compartments put cardiac patients on diuretic medication at risk for heart failure, it is imperative to closely monitor their hemodynamic condition. A possible unidentified renal disease should be looked into and the treatment should be stopped if a diuretic is unable to cause diuresis.^[76,77]

1.12 CONTRAINDICATION

Severe dehydration or established anuria is a contraindication for any type of diuretic. Patients with known hypersensitivity to any of the diuretic agents are contraindicated to receive the same drug. Diuretics are contraindicated in severe electrolyte derangement and should not be administered until a detected electrolyte abnormality is corrected. Loop and thiazide diuretics are contraindicated in patients already diagnosed with gout.^[78]

Loop diuretics (except ethacrynic acid), thiazide diuretics, and CAIs are all sulfonamide derivatives and were generally regarded as contraindicated in sulfa-allergy patients. Recent evidence suggests otherwise, and several reports of instances of uneventful use of sulfa-diuretic use in documented sulfa-allergy patients exist.^[79] In conclusion, sulfa-allergic individuals can only be cautiously provided diuretics and antibiotics with a low risk of cross-allergenicity with sulfonamide non-antibiotics.

It is a relative contraindication for sulfonamide non-antibiotics, but a confirmed allergy to any of the sulfonamide diuretic medicines itself should be regarded as an absolute contraindication.^[80,81] Patients with severe hyponatremia, hypotension, azotemia, oliguria/anuria, hepatic coma, hypokalemia (should be given only after correction), and hypotension should not take loop diuretics.

Additionally, it is not recommended in any circumstance, including surgery, if fluid loss is anticipated. While torsemide is category B and generally safe during pregnancy, furosemide

and bumetanide are category C medications.^[82]

Although thiazide diuretics cause hyperglycemia, are they not recommended for hypertensive individuals due to the possibility of developing diabetes or exacerbating preexisting diabetes? In individuals with hypertension, a condition predominantly treated to lower the high risk of cardiovascular death, thiazides are essential first-line medication.

In terms of lowering systolic blood pressure and reaching desired blood pressure levels, chlorthalidone, a thiazide-like diuretic, has proven to be more effective than hydrochlorothiazide, a thiazide-type diuretic. Additionally, numerous clinical trials have demonstrated that chlorthalidone significantly lowers the risk of unfavorable CV events when compared to other anti-hypertensives. Furthermore, compared to other anti-hypertensive medications, chlorthalidone has been demonstrated to result in the fewest clinical occurrences of diabetes.

The beneficial anti-hypertensive effects of low-dose (12.5 mg) chlorthalidone in a hypertensive population with preexisting diabetes exceed the risk of glucose intolerance and will be especially advantageous for youthful, non-obese individuals.

The highest class I recommendation for treating diabetics with hypertension is to utilize thiazide/thiazide-like diuretics in combination with a RAS blocker, according to the 2018 ESC guidelines on hypertension.^[83,84]

Although recent reports support the use of thiazides as an anti-hypertensive (even if GFR is less than 30 mL/min), guidelines advised against their use in patients with severe stage 4 or stage 5 CKD because the thiazide's lowering mechanism is unrelated to its diuretic function in the kidney.

However, when diuresis is the primary action needed in CKD patients, thiazides are contraindicated; loop diuretics are the better option. Metolazone, a thiazide diuretic that can be used for diuresis in CKD, is the lone exception.^[85,86]

When hyperkalemia (K^+ levels greater than 5 mEq/L) occurs, K^+ -sparing diuretics should not be used until the underlying disease has been addressed. Due to the danger of hyperkalemia, PSDs are contraindicated in patients with advanced renal failure or chronic kidney disease (CKD); this is especially true when GFR is less than 30 mL/min/1.73 m²,

which corresponds to CKD stages 4 and 5.^[87,88]

While eplerenone is classified as a category B medicine, spiro lactone is classified as a pregnancy category C medication and, along with triamterene, should be avoided during pregnancy.

Acetazolamide is contraindicated in hyperchloremic metabolic acidosis (see adverse effects), and when contemplating acetazolamide for treatment in severe chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, great care should be used.^[89]

Mannitol is mostly eliminated by the kidneys, and because it might result in osmotic nephropathy, it should be administered carefully in patients who have renal impairment. Mannitol-induced intravascular volume overload is contraindicated in people with heart and renal failure since it may cause concerns.

Patients with severe dehydration, significant cranial hemorrhage, or a history of mannitol hypersensitivity should not take this medication. An initial test dose is necessary to confirm the diuretic response when mannitol is used to treat anuria.^[90]

1.14 DRUG INTERACTION

Salicylates have the ability to displace acetazolamide from plasma protein, increasing the amount of free acetazolamide in the plasma and inducing toxicity due to the inhibition of RBC carbonic anhydrase. Since acetazolamide might exacerbate metabolic acidosis, it should not be used to alkalinize urine after a salicylate overdose.^[91,92]

GFR, RAAS, water and salt secretion, and systemic and renal vasodilation are all modulated by prostaglandins. When nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) inhibit them in a hypertensive patient, the effects of antihypertensive treatments, such as diuretics, may be suppressed.

Under normal conditions, NSAIDs have little effect on controlling renal functions; however, when combined with loop or thiazide diuretics, they can soften the natriuretic response, lower GFR, and suppress renin synthesis, which can result in acute renal failure.^(93,94) Other ototoxic medications, such as aminoglycosides or chemotherapeutic agents containing platinum, can intensify the ototoxic effects of loop diuretics.^[95]

Hypokalemia brought on by diuretics may make digitalis-induced arrhythmia more likely.^[96] Because digoxin and K⁺ ions fight for the same binding site on the heart's Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase pump, digoxin's action is unopposed in diuretic-induced hypokalemia, which can result in deadly arrhythmias.^[97]

While every diuretic that causes hypokalemia can have this impact, loop diuretics are the most dangerous when compared to other diuretic classes; nonetheless, hydrochlorothiazide was the most dangerous when used alone.^[98]

Digoxin and hypokalemia-inducible diuretics should therefore not be taken together as this can be harmful. Similarly, because quinidine can intensify the cardiovascular effects of thiazide-induced hypokalemia, doctors should refrain from using it.^[99]

Bendroflumethiazide can cause calcium retention, and care is necessary when administered along with calcium supplements or vitamin D.⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ Thiazides can cause lithium accumulation when the drugs are co-administered as they can increase lithium reabsorption in the PT.^[101]

RAAS inhibiting agents like ACEIs, ARBs, beta-blockers, NSAIDs, or aliskiren can result in a small amount of potassium retention, and their concomitant use with PSDs may cause hyperkalemia and hence a relative contraindication.^[102] PSDs apparently must not be administered along with another PSD to avoid the risk of dangerous hyperkalemia.

1.15 MONITORING

Extracellular fluid volume, urine output, electrolyte levels in plasma and urine, body weight, acid-base status, serum glucose, and blood pressure must all be carefully assessed when taking diuretics. Patients with metabolic, hepatic, cardiovascular, or renal diseases as well as the elderly should receive special attention. Blood urea nitrogen and creatinine levels need to be monitored, and diuretic-induced hypovolemia in prerenal azotemia is concerning.

Loop diuretics carry the danger of ototoxicity, hence extra care must be used. In order to assess the impact of loop diuretics on auditory functions on an individual basis following a certain duration of therapy, baseline auditory tests are required, particularly when planning large bolus doses at high infusion rates.

The potential of switching to a different diuretic therapy should be considered in the event of any negative consequences, and periodic sequential monitoring of auditory capabilities is also

advised.^[103]

Patients taking diuretics should have their clinical cardiac state evaluated, particularly if they have MI, HF, or other cardiac problems, since the sudden increase in fluid shift between the compartments increases the risk of developing HF.

Diuretics should be stopped if they don't boost urine production because this could be a sign of unidentified underlying renal disease.

Because frequent mannitol administration might exacerbate cerebral edema, it should be given every 6 to 8 hours.

1.16 DIURETIC ABUSE

Since diuretics are not strictly regulated, there is a greater chance that they may be abused, especially by athletes who may take them to lose weight quickly or to hide the use of other illegal substances. It is forbidden for athletes to take diuretics.

The World Anti-Doping Agency regularly screens athletes for it, and athletes need a previous exemption for medicinal use. When combined with excessive physical activity, as seen in sportsmen, chronic usage of this kind can have fatal consequences for cardiovascular and thermoregulatory systems.^[104]

When bulimics attempt to purge food, they may abuse diuretics, which can result in pseudo-Bartter syndrome.^[105] Along with laxatives, diuretics can also be abused by psychotic individuals.^[106]

1.17 DIURETIC IN DIAGNOSIS

Furosemide/Fludrocortisone test (FFT)

For the diagnosis of distal renal tubular acidosis (dRTA), furosemide and the mineralocorticoid fludrocortisone have become a common combination. The inability of alpha-intercalated cells to secrete H⁺ ions in the distal tubules causes a deficiency in urine acidification in dRTA (see the mechanism of action of PSDs).

There are four distinct forms of dRTA, which are typically identified using the ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) loading test. However, the test is occasionally discontinued because of unsettling gastrointestinal symptoms following injection. Urine becomes acidic when NH₄Cl

and HCO_3^+ ions combine in the liver to create urea, which lowers blood HCO_3^+ levels and puts stress on the kidneys to reabsorb more HCO_3^+ ions in exchange for H^+ ions.^[107]

Systemic metabolic acidosis may result from this test in patients with dRTA because the kidneys' inability to reabsorb HCO_3^+ ions is caused by a deficiency in H^+ ion secretion. The test is deemed positive for dRTA if the pH of the urine is higher than 5.3. FFT is a more acceptable and well-tolerated substitute. Fludrocortisone, a mineralocorticoid, promotes H^+ ion secretion via alpha-intercalated cells and improves Na^+ reabsorption via ENaCs.

Furosemide also increases the distal transport of Na^+ ions. Thus, without the metabolic acidosis brought on by NH_4Cl , this combination can acidify the urine. Patients with dRTA are diagnosed because they are unable to lower their urine pH, while those without the condition have a pH of less than 5.3 with FFT.^[108,109]

Mannitol challenge test (MCT)

When diagnosing asthma, mannitol may be used as an agent in a challenge test. When dry mannitol powder is inhaled during this test, the bronchial periciliary liquid becomes hyperosmolar, causing cell shrinking to bring the osmolality back to normal.

This further causes smooth muscle constriction by causing inflammatory cells, especially mast cells, to secrete pro-inflammatory chemicals. An readily induced active airway inflammation, indicating airway hyperresponsiveness, is shown by a 15% drop in forced expiratory volume in the first second (FEV1). Despite being a highly safe test, MCT has a high specificity but only a modest sensitivity for identifying asthma.

Comparatively speaking, MCT has a higher specificity than direct bronchial challenge tests like histamine or methacholine challenge tests.^[110]

1.18 TOXICITY

Reversible ototoxicity (manifested as sensory neural hearing loss, tinnitus) can be caused by ischemia in stria vascularis and by inhibiting NKCC1 channels in stria vascularis by loop diuretics, which improves with discontinuation of the drug.

Deafness and tinnitus from loop diuretics most frequently occur when administering large bolus doses in an acute setting, such as when using furosemide in acute kidney injury. The resulting ototoxicity is, therefore, due to the higher serum concentrations of the drug

achieved. Ethacrynic acid is the most ototoxic drug in this group.^[111]

There are reports of hydrochlorothiazide, furosemide, spironolactone, and triamterene, causing hepatotoxicity, but there is no suggestion of diuretic class effect.^[112,113] There have been reports of diuretic-induced kidney damage, and because senior patients' thirst response is less sensitive, this damage is most severe in these patients.

Acute renal failure can result from diuretics, which are also linked to an elevated risk when renal blood flow is impaired in diseases such as nephrotic syndrome, hepatic cirrhosis, and congestive heart failure.

Because greater diuretic dosages are linked to pathological damage of the glomerular basement membrane, dose dependency also plays a role. Diuretics should not be used with other nephrotoxic medications since they can cause vacuolar degeneration of tubular epithelial cells.^[114]

1.19 CLINICAL USES OF DIURETICS

Which diuretic, for which patient and why?

Both oedematous and non-oedematous disorders are treated with diuretics. It is not necessary to go into great length about the pathophysiology of oedema here, although an Morrison's summary deserves recognition. Oedema can be seen in nephrotic syndrome, heart failure, renal failure, and hepatic cirrhosis ascites.

Hypertension, nephrolithiasis, hypercalcaemia, and diabetes insipidus are among the non-oedematous conditions. Each patient's unique set of circumstances will determine which diuretic is best for them, including the patient's heart failure (a patient may also have chronic kidney disease), the agent's efficacy, metabolism, and adverse effects.

As reference to helps indicate, one cannot rely on chemical grouping as a guide (as one can with oral hypoglycaemic drugs). Three categories of diuretics including sulphonamides, which have completely different renal pharmacologies.

Benzothiadiazines, sulphamoyl benzoates, acetazolamide, and the inhibitor of carbonic anhydrase are among them. The first of these is furosemide, which is chemically 4-chloro-N-furfuryl-5-sulphamoyl anthranilic acid and was discovered in 1964.

Furosemide's 4-chloro-5-sulphamoyl substitution of the benzene ring is thought to reflect a thiazide, as seen. However, the existence of a monocyclic system with a furfuryl substitution at position 2 gives the drug the "high ceiling" activity of a loop diuretic rather than a thiazide.

Bumetanide, an agent 40 times more effective than furosemide on a weight basis, was created by substituting a butylamino at position 3 with a phenoxy group at position 4. Its absorption approached 80 percent of 100%.

1.20 BIOCHEMICAL DISTURBANCE DUE TO DIURETICS

As mentioned in the sections before, there are metabolic risks associated with using diuretics. The common metabolic side effects of diuretics are employ.

Hyponatraemia is a common condition that is exacerbated in individuals who consume large amounts of water because they were first prescribed a diuretic. Making the clinical distinction between hyponatraemia in individuals with and without oedema is crucial.

Water and salt consumption should be limited in people with cirrhosis, heart failure, and nephrotic syndrome since these conditions increase the volume of extracellular fluid in the body. The mechanism was already explained.

Hyperkalaemia is a potential side effect of potassium-sparing diuretics, but it is more common when combined with an ACE inhibitor or an angiotensin II receptor antagonist. Hyperkalaemia and metabolic acidosis treated with diuretics that spare potassium.

Since they can be bought "over the counter" (such as ibuprofen and "Lo-Salt"), doctors might not be aware that the patient is taking them until they specifically ask. grabbing them.

Both thiazide and loop diuretics can produce hypokalaemia, and doctors should be aware that extra circumstances might occasionally cause a mild hypokalaemia to increase quickly and cause the patient to have symptoms, including cardiac dysrhythmia.

These ailments include a tiny bowel fistula, vomiting, and diarrhea. Medications include corticosteroids, amphotericin, and theophylline in particular, which might worsen hypokalaemia when combined with diuretics.

When administered simultaneously, thiazide and loop diuretics have the potential to

significantly reduce urine magnesium levels.

Overuse of diuretics can result in orthostatic hypotension, which can be especially problematic for senior thiazide users due to a drop in intravascular volume.

Hypochloraemic metabolic alkalosis (together with hyponatraemia, hypokalaemia, and hypomagnesaemia) can be linked to thiazides. They get worse Digoxin poisoning can be triggered by hypokalaemia and NSAID-induced nephrotoxicity.

As sulphonamide-related medications, allergic reactions are expected, and anesthetists should be aware that they enhance the effects of non-depolarizing, neuromuscular-blocking medicines.

Another characteristic of thiazides is that they may result in hyperuricaemia and the development of gout. While only 2% of people on long-term thiazides develop clinical gout, 50% of patients experience hyperuricaemia.

Most likely, two systems are at work. As organic acids, uric acid and diuretics probably compete with each other for the transport mechanisms that transfer them from the blood into the tubular fluid.

Secondly, decreased glomerular filtration may result from the extracellular fluid volume being depleted by diuretics. and enhanced proximal tubule absorption of the majority of solutes, including urate.

In addition to sharing an electrolyte imbalance with thiazides, loop diuretics also increase the effects of non-depolarizing neuromuscular blocking drugs, aminoglycosides, and cephalosporin antibiotics.

One can easily locate additional details about side effects in extensive clinical pharmacology textbooks Porphyria patients have unique needs, and several websites offer often updated information on "unsafe" medications, such as diuretics.

1.21 FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

Recently, a novel class of diuretics was identified, posing an intriguing challenge to medical research. They are known as AQP modulators, and since a patent application for the first in its class was filed, they are probably going to be used commercially.

The possibility of "gates" enabling the quick reabsorption of water by renal tubular cells has long intrigued physiologists.

The lipid bilayer of the cell membrane, which was first described in 1935 as the Danielelli-Davson model, is essentially a hydrophobic barrier that diffusion will only allow a very little trickle of water to pass through.

The discovery of water channels known as AQPs⁸¹ in the early 1990s provided an explanation for how water may move through a membrane at a rate of about three billion molecules per second for each AQP channel.

A number of the AQP family members permit urea and glycerol permeability as well. Whereas AQP2 is found in the main cells of the collecting duct, where it shuttles between intracellular vesicles and the apical membrane in response to vasopressin, AQP1 is mostly found in the proximal tubule and descending thin limb of the loop of Henle.

Elevated AQP2 activity plays a role in the pathophysiology of heart failure, nephrotic syndrome, and cirrhosis (all illnesses for which diuretics are prescribed approach management).

The AQP2 gene is mutated in nephrogenic diabetes insipidus. Mouse knockout models have been created in order to investigate the potential for AQP expression and function modulation.

According to Verkman's assessment, research on mice phenotypes suggests that AQP expression/function modulators may have a variety of clinical applications. uses include diuretics and the management of cancer, obesity, glaucoma, epilepsy, and cerebral oedema.

After his 1988 discovery, Dr. Peter Agre was granted the Chemistry Nobel Prize in 2003, after around 15 years. There are eleven identified AQP channels (AQP0–AQP10), albeit not all of them are found in humans.

A study conducted on oocytes that express AQP1 and AQP4 revealed that AQP1 and AQP4 water permeability is inhibited by one of the 45 produced bumetanide derivatives. AqB01385 is the 4-aminopyridine carboxamide counterpart of bumetanide.

It is believed to obstruct the AQP water pore at the cytoplasmic side in order to accomplish

its blocking effect, and the internal pore occluding binding site has been determined. Most notably, AQP4 channel expression has been detected in astroglial cells at the blood–brain barrier interface And AQP1 in the kidney. AQP1 channels are located in the choroid plexus implicated in cerebrospinal fluid secretion in the mammalian brain.

1.22 PREVENTION

- **Reduce salt intake:** A low-salt diet can help reduce blood pressure and prevent hypokalaemia, a potentially life-threatening condition that can cause abnormal heartbeats.
- **Increase potassium intake:** You can take potassium supplements or eat more potassium-rich foods.
- **Take a potassium-sparing diuretic:** A potassium-sparing diuretic can reduce the risk of hypokalaemia.
- **Adjust your diuretic dose:** Reducing the dose of your diuretic can help prevent hypokalaemia.
- **Switch diuretics:** Switching to a different diuretic can help reduce side effect.

1.23 ENHANCING HEALTHCARE TEAM OUTCOMES

Diuretic therapy, while typically well-tolerated, requires the comprehensive effort of an interprofessional medical team, including clinicians, specialists, NPs and PAs, nurses, and pharmacists.

Patient education plays a crucial role and adequate knowledge of the adverse effects, dietary, and lifestyle modifications necessary while on diuretics. Patients (especially in an outpatient setting) must understand to report any changes in their compliance pattern or any adverse effect thereof.

Adherence to strict treatment protocols and timely intake of the drug, and avoiding any overdosing when the patients miss their dosing will significantly improve the clinical course and the effectiveness of the diuretic agent. Nurses, as immediate caregivers, should be cognizant of the adverse effects of diuretics and should be able to alert the treating clinician if a patient's condition worsens.^[115]

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Salim Janmohamed, Pierre. Marc, *etal.*,(2006)^[116]

Aldosterone is increasingly considered to have a fundamental role in the pathophysiology of

cardiovascular disease. Primary aldosteronism is a much more common cause of secondary hypertension than once suspected, accounting for approximately 10% of cases. Screening for primary aldosteronism should be considered even in the presence of normokalaemia. The non-classical effects of aldosterone, some of which are transcription-independent, may be of similar or greater importance than its traditional effects on the kidney.

Treatment of primary aldosteronism should be specific and aim to ameliorate all hormone-related effects of aldosterone, not just the most obvious manifestation of hypertension.

Mineralocorticoid antagonism, shown to lead to significant additional survival advantage in heart failure, offers the best prospect for achieving therapeutic goals. For the increasing proportion of patients with primary aldosteronism suitable for long-term medical treatment, mineralocorticoid receptor blockade (better tolerated with eplerenone) should be considered the most appropriate choice of treatment, pending the development of better alternatives

2. D. L. Jain a, A. M. Baheti b , S. R. Parakh b , S. P. Ingale b , P.L.Ingale b etal., (2007)^[117]

In rats, the antacid and diuretic properties of various extracts and ash from *Musa sapientum* L. (Musaceae) peels were investigated. According to the study, the ash exhibits good antacid activity. According to Lipschitz et al. (1943), a diuretic investigation was conducted using ash from the peel of *Musa* fruit and successive aqueous, ethanolic, and petroleum ether extracts. *sapientum* L. were investigated for their diuretic properties. In comparison to normal saline, the 6-hour acute study of successive aqueous, ethanolic extracts, and peel ash revealed an increase in urine volume and K⁺ ion excretion. Sodium, potassium, and chloride levels in the urine were measured using flame photometry and titrimetry, respectively.

In our experimental model, ash and ethanolic extract showed evidence of diuretic potentials in normal rats, while ash may have good antacid activity based on observed results. The pathological Prior to being recommended for use as diuretic medicines, their harmful effects on essential organs and examination needed further research.

3. S. Abdala, D. Martín-Herrera, D. Benjumea, P. Pérez-Paz etal.,(2008)^[118]

Both the alcohol extract and hot water infusions considerably raised water excretion rates in a dose- dependent manner. Although potassium excretion was significantly lower when using the alcohol extract than when using the infusion, the electrolytic excretion was likewise dose-

dependent.

Smilax canariensis exhibits a significant diuretic impact that seems to be connected to both the presence of polar chemical molecules and its potassium concentration. The current findings offer a quantitative foundation for understanding how the people of the Canary Islands have used *Smilax canariensis* as a diuretic in traditional folk medicine.

4. **W.D. Ratnasooriya, T.S.P. Fernando, R.A.A.R Ranatunga, et al., (2009)^[119]**

This study set out to assess Sri Lankan black tea's (*Camellia sinensis* L.) diuretic properties. Using high-grown Dust grade No. 1 tea, which is extensively eaten by tea drinkers globally, this was evaluated in rats. Rats that had been starved for 24 hours but then hydrated with 15 milliliters of isotonic saline were given varying doses of hot black tea brew (BTB) (84, 167, 501, or 1336 mg/ml, respectively, equivalent to 1.5, 3, 9, and 24 cups). Their urine output was then tracked cumulatively at hourly intervals for 6 hours. Furosemide (13 mg/kg) was the reference medication utilized. The findings demonstrated that BTB caused mild to moderate, dose-dependent, and significant ($P < 0.05$) diuresis (beginning at 167 mg/ml). This diuretic action started working within two hours and lasted for only three hours. Additionally, BTB considerably ($P < 0.05$) raised the frequency of urination overall.

Additionally, BTB's diuretic action was 45% weaker than furosemide's. Black tea's decaffeination virtually eliminated the diuresis. There was no urinary K^+ loss, and the BTB's diuresis was only caused by a 55% increase in urine Na^+ excretion. Furthermore, neither tolerance nor toxicity (general, renal, and hepatic) were brought on by the long-term, daily dosage of BTB. It has been determined that BTB, which is made from high-grown Dust grade No. 1 tea from Sri Lanka, has mild to moderate diuretic activity that is safe, has a quick onset, and lasts for a short while.

5. **K. R. W. Abeywickrama, W.D. Ratnasooriya, A. M. T. Amarakoon, et al., (2010)^[120]**

Significant ($P < 0.05$) and dose-dependent diuretic activity was induced by BTI administration, and this activity changed depending on the tea grown at different agroclimatic elevations. Diuretic activity started quickly, peaked at two hours, and continued until four hours. Additionally, the frequency of micturition increased in a dose-dependent manner, peaking at two hours. There was a clear correlation between tea's caffeine level and its diuretic effects. GFR and urine Na^+ levels rose in tandem with BTI-induced diuresis. Inhibition of carbonic anhydrase [with decreased $Cl^- / (Na^+ + K^+)$ ratio] and aldosterone secretion (with

increased Na + /K + ratio) as well as thiazide type diuretic action (measured with increased Na + /Cl⁻ ratio) were the two mechanisms by which BTI's diuretic effect was mediated.

6. **Rebecca Vigen, Rick A Weideman, et al., (2011)**^[121]

The administration of hydrochlorothiazide for hypertension was changed in the 1980s from high-dose (50 mg/day) to low-dose (12.5–25 mg/day) therapy. However, only high doses (≥ 50 mg/day) were used in randomized controlled trials (RCT) for the prevention of calcium-containing kidney stones (CCKS). We postulated that these procedures have led to hydrochlorothiazide dosages being underdosed in order to prevent CCKS. Individuals who completed a 24-hour urinary stone risk factor analysis and had a filled prescription for thiazide diuretics were eligible. Those that provided proof of a thiazide prescription for CCKS underwent additional analysis. Of the 107 patients, 4 received treatment with indapamide, 1 with chlorthalidone, and 102 with hydrochlorothiazide. Only 35% of hydrochlorothiazide-treated patients received 50 mg/day; a dose previously shown to reduce stone recurrence. Fifty-two percent were prescribed 25 mg and 13% 12.5 mg daily, doses that were not studied in RCT. Evidence-based hydrochlorothiazide use was suboptimal regardless of where the patient received care (Nephrology or Endocrinology clinic). In a small subset of patients ($n = 6$) with 24-h urinary calcium excretion measured at baseline and after 2 hydrochlorothiazide doses (25 and ≥ 50 mg), there was a trend toward decreased urinary calcium excretion as the dose was increased from 25 to ≥ 50 mg/day ($p = 0.051$). Low-dose hydrochlorothiazide was often used for prevention of CCKS despite the fact that there is no evidence that it is effective in this setting. This may have resulted from a practice pattern of using lower doses for hypertension therapy or a lack of knowledge of RCT results in treatment of CCKS.

S Mohanraj, Santhoshkumar C, A. Chandran, et al.,(2012)^[122]

The purpose of the current study was to examine the diuretic effects of both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of the entire *Leptadenia reticulata* plant in normal rats. Experimental rats were given oral doses of 100 mg/kg p.o. of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of whole *Leptadenia reticulata* plants. In the trial, furosemide (100 mg/kg) served as the positive control. Urine volume, salt, potassium, and chloride concentration were measured in order to assess the extract's diuretic impact. Both the ethanolic and aqueous extracts considerably raised urine volume when compared to the control group, but this impact was not as strong as that of furosemide. Both the treated and standard groups showed a significant increase in renal

clearance of sodium, potassium, and chloride ions.

7. José Ramón Montejano-Rodríguez , Georgina Almaguer-Vargas,etal.,(2013)^[123]

The diuretic activity of some plants has been attributed to the presence of flavonoids, and *G. seemannii* Peyr. has a relatively large concentration of ellagitannins. This could be responsible for the effect demonstrated herein, which was similar to that produced by the reference drug furosemide. The mechanism of action of furosemide is by inducing a loss of water through the inhibition of NaCl reabsorption. The results suggest that this receptor-mediated mechanism may account for the diuretic effect of *G. seemannii* Peyr. as well.

8. Fidèle Ntchapda, Djedouboum Abakar, Blaise Kom,etal.,(2014)^[124]

Urine volume increased significantly 24 hours after the *F. glumosa* aqueous extract leaves were administered as a single dose. Increased diuresis and moderate elevation of natriuresis are tubular in origin, as evidenced by the animals' stable aldosterone levels, lack of correlation with sodium plasma levels, and increased clearance of free water. Urine became alkaline due to the extract's rise in Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻, which also demonstrated a potent inhibitory action on saluretics and carbonic anhydrase.

9. AMINAH DALIMUNTHE1, URIP HARAHAPE1,etal.,(2015)^[125]

The purpose of this study was to assess the diuretic activity of several *Picria fel-terrae* leaf extracts utilizing solvents such as n-hexane, ethyl acetate, and ethanol. The diuretic efficacy of the extracts was assessed by measuring urine volume and electrolyte (Na⁺, K⁺) concentrations in male Wistar rats given doses of 400 and 800 mg/kg bw. When n-hexane extract was administered at a dose of 800 mg/kg bw, urine volume increased significantly compared to normal control groups. All extracts increased sodium excretion as well. The n-hexane extract had a stronger diuretic impact than the other extracts. Conclusion: The leaves of *Picria fel-terrae* contain diuretic properties. Keywords: *Picria fel-terrae* Lour, Diuresis, Urine Electrolyte.

10. Wayne L , Miller, etal.,(2016)^[126]

In patients with heart failure, volume regulation, assessment, and management continue to be fundamental concerns. The goal of this debate is to start a new dialogue about the biology of congestion in congestive heart failure and the techniques we use to measure volume overload status. Reviews of peer-reviewed historical and modern literature are provided. Patients suffering from chronic heart failure still primarily face problems with volume overload and

fluid congestion. The idea that intravascular fluid buildup is the only explanation for the pathophysiology's complexity is insufficient. Strategies for managing volume must consider the dynamics of fluid redistribution from venous splanchnic beds to the central pulmonary circulation as well as the interactions between interstitial and intravascular fluid compartments. Clinical bedside evaluations and right heart hemodynamic assessments can alert clinicians of changes in volume status, but only the quantitative measurement of total blood volume can help identify the heterogeneity in plasma volume and red blood cell mass that are features of volume overload in patients with chronic heart failure and help guide individualized, appropriate therapy-not all volume overload is the same.

11. Amelework Eshetu Melka , Eyasu Makonnen, Asfaw Debella, et al.,(2016)^[127]

The current study looked into the diuretic efficacy and acute toxicity profile of the crude aqueous extract and solvent fraction of *Thymus serrulatus* leaves in saline-treated Swiss albino mice. Mice of either sex were divided into six groups (five per group). The control group got normal saline (25 mL/kg), while the reference group was given hydrochlorothiazide (10 mg/kg). Groups III–VI received the test drugs orally at doses of 125, 250, 500, and 1,000 mg/kg, respectively. At the end of the fifth hour, urine was collected, and the total amount of pee excreted by each animal was recorded. Urinary Na⁺ and K⁺ concentrations were measured, and the Na⁺/K⁺ ratio was computed to allow for group comparisons.

12. Eusuf Al Huda1, Jiban Debnath, et al.,(2017)^[128]

This study examined the diuretic effects of aqueous extracts from dried *Centella asiatica* leaves on normal rats. *Centella asiatica* (L.) is a perennial herb with a slight scent and is used since ancient times, it has been used for its numerous medical benefits. Herbal formulations are becoming increasingly popular globally due to their perceived safety and lack of negative effects compared to synthetic alternatives. **Materials and Methods:** The plant's leaves were washed, dried under shade, and extracted with distilled water. The extracts were dried and concentrated using a rotary vacuum evaporator. Lipschitz et al. used metabolic cages to assess diuretic activity.

13. Rameshkumar Angappan, Arul Ananth Devanesan, et al.,(2018)^[129]

A diuretic medicine increases urine excretion and is commonly used to treat edema, congestive heart failure, hypertension, and liver/kidney issues. Today's marketed diuretic medications include thiazide (chlorothiazide, hydrochlorothiazide), loop (furosemide,

bumetanide), K⁺ sparing (amioloride, eplerenone), and CA inhibitors (acetazolamide, dichlorphenamide).

Commercial diuretics can cause side effects including hypokalemia, metabolic alkalosis, hypovolemia, hypotension, fever, cough, irregular bleeding, abnormal weight loss, nausea, and vomiting. Medicinal plant-based diuretics are more effective than commercially available options.

14. Jayanthi MK, Siddamma Amoghimath, *etal.*,(2018)^[130]

To investigate in wistar albino rats the diuretic effects of an ethanolic extract of delonix regia leaves. Wistar albino rats were chosen at random and split into four groups with approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IAEC). Group 1 was given normal saline (25 ml/kg) as a negative control on the day of the experiment, Group 2 was given furosemide (20 mg/kg body weight), Group 3 was given ethanonic extract of delonix regia (100 mg/kg), and Group 4 was given ethanonic extract of delonix regia (200 mg/kg). When taken at doses of 100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg of body weight, delonix regia increases the excretion of water and sodium, respectively.

15. Robert H, Glew Zeid, J Khitan, *etal.*,(2018)^[131]

Three ideas are involved in the management of body fluid balance, which is a major concern in both health and sickness. The first idea is described in terms of the body fluids' tonicity and concerns the link between total body water (TBW) and total effective solute. Cell volume variations are mostly caused by disturbances in tonicity, which can have a significant impact on the survival and functionality of brain cells. Tonicity is influenced by solutes that are almost primarily distributed in the extracellular compartment (mostly sodium salts) and the intracellular compartment (mostly potassium salts). Solutes that are dispersed in TBW do not affect tonicity. The second idea in body fluid balance has to do with controlling and quantifying deviations in extracellular volume and sodium-salt balance. Extracellular volume estimation of extracellular volume is more complex and error prone than measurement of TBW. A key function of extracellular volume, which is defined as the effective arterial blood volume (EABV), is to ensure adequate perfusion of cells and organs. Other factors, including cardiac output, total and regional capacity of both arteries and veins, Starling forces in the capillaries, and gravity also affect the EABV. Collectively, these factors interact closely with extracellular volume and some of them undergo substantial changes in certain acute and chronic severe illnesses. Their changes result not only in extracellular volume expansion, but

in the need for a larger extracellular volume compared with that of healthy individuals. Assessing extracellular volume in severe illness is challenging because the estimates of this volume by commonly used methods are prone to large errors in many illnesses. In addition, the optimal extracellular volume may vary from illness to illness, is only partially based on volume measurements by traditional methods, and has not been determined for each illness. Further research is needed to determine optimal extracellular volume levels in several illnesses. For these reasons, extracellular volume in severe illness merits a separate third concept of body fluid balance.

16. Kemeta Azambou David Romain¹, Ntchapda Fidele¹, *etal.*,(2019)^[132]

Five different dosages of the aqueous extract of *Ceiba pentandra* leaves were used: 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 mg/kg. Eight batches or groups of five rats each were then created from the chosen animals. The amount of food, water, and urine excretion were resolved. 24 hours following treatment, the rats were slaughtered (sacrificed), and heparinated tubes were used to collect the blood. A spectrophotometer was used to measure the levels of creatinine, urea, glucose, ALAT, ASAT, and electrolytes in the blood and/or urine. Similar to furosemide and amiloride, aqueous leaf extract caused rats' urine excretion volume to rise significantly ($p < 0.05$) and in a dose-dependent manner when compared to the negative control group.

17. Gebrelibanos Gebremichael Welu, *etal.*,(2020)^[133]

When compared to the water fraction, the 400 mg/kg dose of the crude hydromethanolic extract, ethyl acetate, and chloroform fractions caused a substantial diuresis ($P < 0.001$). In comparison to the standard furosemide, the hydromethanolic extract at 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg also produced observable diuresis ($P < 0.001$). When compared to the aqueous fraction, rats treated with hydromethanolic extract, ethyl acetate, and chloroform fractions exhibited dose-dependent delayed onset and protracted diuresis ($P < 0.05$). When compared to the normal furosemide, the hydromethanolic extract and solvent fractions produced the highest saluretic and natriuretic indices. When compared to the aqueous fraction, rats treated with hydromethanolic extract, ethyl acetate, and chloroform fractions exhibited dose-dependent delayed onset and protracted diuresis ($P < 0.05$). When compared to the normal furosemide, the hydromethanolic extract and solvent fractions produced the highest saluretic and natriuretic indices. Additionally, up to 2000 mg/kg, the crude hydromethanolic extract showed no signs of toxicity. In conclusion. According to this study, rats showed a noticeable

diuretic effect from the hydromethanolic extract and ethyl acetate fraction of *C. myricoides* root bark.

18. sindhura Nagisetty, P. Sirisha, et al.,(2021)^[134]

In a number of clinical settings, diuretics are used to maintain the amount and composition of bodily fluids by increasing urine flow and sodium excretion. Goals: To assess in albino rats the diuretic effects of an alcoholic (AERMI) extract of *Mangifera indica* roots. Methods: Using metabolic cages, the diuretic activity was assessed in five groups of albino rats. Group I was given a vehicle as a normal control, while Group II was given Furosemide (10 mg/Kg, p.o.). Groups III, IV, and V were given low, medium, and high doses of AERMI, and all of the rats were immediately hydrated with saline (15 ml/kg) and put in metabolic cages following extract treatment. After five hours, the total volume of urine collected was measured. Urine's sodium, potassium, and chloride concentrations were calculated. Results: AERMI at 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg considerably increased urine volume and improved sodium, potassium, and chloride elimination when compared to the control group.

Conclusion: AERMI doses of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg as well as frusemide have been shown to enhance urine production and raise sodium, potassium, and chloride concentrations.

19. Tufer S., Engidawork E., Ayele A.G., et al.,(2021)^[135]

Extract from *Croton macrostachyus* (Euphorbiaceae) has long been used in folk medicine to treat a variety of illnesses, including edematous diseases. In this work, rats that were given saline were used to test the diuretic properties of leaf extracts (80% methanol and 80% aqueous) from *Croton macrostachyus*.

Techniques: Rats of both sexes were divided into eight groups of eight animals each at random. After loading of normal saline (15 mL/kg), the animals were given with vehicle (distilled water), standard (furosemide 10 mg/kg), and three dosages (100, 200, and 400 mg/kg) of aqueous and 80% methanol leaf extracts. Then, as evaluation parameters, pH, electrolyte concentration, and urine volume were assessed. Urine Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻ concentrations were measured, and ratios of Na⁺:K⁺ and Cl⁻:Na⁺ + K⁺ were computed to uncover potential processes. **Results:** The aqueous extract at 200 mg/kg had produced significant diuresis by hour 3, while the same dose of 80% methanol extract had produced substantial diuresis by the end of hour 4. Both extracts at 400 mg/kg produced significant diuresis from hour 2 to hour 5. In terms of effect on electrolysis, 400 mg/kg aqueous extract

produced significant natriuresis, and a kaliuresis effect was observed for both extracts at higher doses and 200 mg/kg aqueous extract. **Conclusion:** The findings collectively indicated that both aqueous and 80% methanol extract showed significant diuretic activity, thereby justifying the plant's traditional use as a diuretic agent.

20. Farah AL-MAMOORI, Talal ABURJAI, Feras EL-HAJJ, et al., (2022)^[136]

The health benefits of medicinal plants are constantly growing, and they are a rich source of compounds that prevent disease. Numerous medical conditions can benefit from traditional treatments, but their full potential cannot be realized until they have undergone scientific validation. Thus, the purpose of the current study was to assess the *Teucrium polium* L. ethanolic extract's diuretic effects on Wistar rats. In a Soxhlet device, 70% ethanol was used to extract the ground aerial portions of *T. polium*. Four groups of Wistar rats were created: one control group and three treatment groups that received ethanolic extracts of *T. polium* (200 and 400 mg/kg) and a reference diuretic drug (furosemide at 10 mg/kg). The amount of urine and electrolyte (Na⁺, K⁺, and Cl⁻) excretion was measured five hours after the injection. Carbonic anhydrase inhibition, diuretic and saluretic activity, and the diuretic index were also calculated. The findings demonstrated that the treatment groups receiving 200 and 400 mg/kg had a substantial Both urine volume and moderate diuretic activity increased ($P < 0.05$) by 0.78 and 0.99, respectively. The excretion of K⁺ and Cl⁻ was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) in the *T. polium* (400 mg/kg) ethanolic extract group than in the control group.

Additionally, the 400 mg/kg treatment group's saluretic activity increased to 528.0 (as determined by the Na⁺+K⁺) in comparison to the control group's 308.0 saluretic activity.

21. F. Rafiquea, M. N. Mushtaqa, H. Ahmedb, et al., (2023)^[137]

The purpose of this study was to investigate linalyl acetate's (LA) diuretic action. A vital phyto-constituent of many plants, LA is an essential oil. In this work, the levels of various electrolytes and pH in the urine of experimental rats were measured in order to investigate acute and chronic diuretic actions. Five groups of rats were created. In order to assess LA's diuretic capacity, three groups were administered varying doses of the drug—25, 50, and 75 mg/kg intraperitoneally—while the control group received 10 mg/kg normal saline and the treatment group received 10 mg/kg furosemide. The urine volume was measured for six hours in the case of acute diuretic activity and six days in the case of chronic diuretic activity. Furthermore, by contrasting atropine, L-NAME, and indomethacin, the fundamental mechanism of the diuretic action was also investigated. Each group had six rats, and the

findings were calculated as the \pm standard error of the mean for each group.

Statistical analysis was performed using Variance Analysis. The LA 75 mg/kg dose had effects that were similar to those of furosemide, according to the data. Furthermore, compared to atropine, this study showed that muscarinic receptors are involved in producing diuresis, with prostanoids playing a very minor role and the NO pathway being unaffected by indomethacin and L-NAME, respectively. LA is thought to have anti-diuretic properties. Diuretic effects may be produced by muscarinic receptors.

22. Nardos Lema Wondimu , Mestayet Geta Mengistie,etal.,(2024)^[138]

To test the diuretic effects of hydromethanolic crude extract (HM) and aqueous (AQ) extracts from *Erica arborea* flowers in mice, as well as the solvent fractions of the HM extract. Mice were given solvent fractions of HM extracts of *E. coli* as well as AQ and HM crude extracts. *arborea* flowers at oral dosages ranging from 100 to 400 mg/kg, including HXF (n-hexane fraction), EAF (ethyl acetate fraction), and AQF (aqueous fraction). Over the course of five hours, the effects of these extracts and solvent fractions on salt and urine excretion were compared to those of a typical medication (furosemide 10 mg/kg) and the solvent used for reconstitution. When compared to the AQ crude extract, the HM crude extract at a lower dose (100 mg/kg) dramatically enhanced urine volume and salt output beginning in the third hour. For EAF, comparable results were seen. Notably, the salt and urine excretion profiles of the HM extract and its EAF at 400 mg/kg were similar to those of the usual medication. Because of their saluretic qualities, this study showed that HM extract and EAF improve diuresis. Additionally, it validates that *Erica arborea* flowers have diuretic properties.

Keywords: mice, urine pH, urine electrolyte, diuresis, and natriuresis

23. Alemante Tafese Beyna, Liknaw Workie Limenh, etal.,(2025)^[139]

The mice were given oral dosages of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg of the solvent fraction and 80% hydro-methanol extract. Over a 5-hour period, the effects of these extracts and solvent fractions were contrasted with a negative control and a common drug (furosemide, 10 mg/kg). The acute oral toxicity test revealed that the extract was safe at a dosage of 2000 mg/kg. Urine volume and sodium excretion were significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased by the 400 mg/kg hydro-methanol extract of *S. lycopersicum* L. leaves in comparison to the negative control. Urine volume and sodium excretion were significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher in the 400 mg/kg aqueous solvent fraction and the standard medication (furosemide 10 mg/kg) than in the negative control.

3. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM

The aim of this research was to determine the Diuretics properties of Plant extract of *Cleome gynandra* and its effect on selected biochemical indices in order to determine the efficiency of this extract in Diuretics.

OBJECTIVES

This study evaluates the Phyto chemical and biochemical parameters of *Cleome gynandra* in Albino Wistar rats for possible Diuretic potential.

4. PLAN OF WORK

5. PLANT PROFILE

CLEOME GYNANDRA

5.1 Synonyms

Cleome gynandra is also known by various synonyms such as

Preferred Scientific Name

Cleome gynandra L.

Preferred Common Name

wild spider flower

Other Scientific Names *Gynandropsis gynandra* (L.) Briq. *Cleome heterotricha* Burch
Cleome pentaphylla L. *Gynandropsis heterotricha* (Burch.) DC. *Gynandropsis pentaphylla* (L.)
Blanco.

5.2 Taxonomical Classification

Table 1: Taxonomical classification.

Kingdom	Plantae
Phylum	Spermatophyta
Subphylum	Angiospermae
Order	Capparidales
Family	Capparaceae
Genus	Cleome
Species	Gynandra
Binominal name	<i>Cleome gynandra</i>

5.3 Common names

Different names of *Cleome gynandra* in different countries have been reported in table

Table 2: Common Names.

Country	Common Names
India	Kurkur
Germany	Senfkapper
Netherland	Kattesnor
Malaysia	Maman
Thailand	Phaksian
Indonesia	Babowan
USA	Small spider flower
South Africa	Tamaleika

5.4 Vernacular names of *Cleome gynandra* in India

Table 3: Vernacular names.

Language	Common names
Tamil	Nal valai
Sanskrit	Psaugandhi
English	Dog mustard
kanada	Nayeetulasi
Hindi	Hulhul
Malayalam	Atunari vela

5.5 Origin and Distribution

Origin

Cleome gynandra grows all over the world and is used as a medicinal plant. It thrives as a weed along the sides of roads and in paddy fields. and in grasslands that are open. It grows naturally throughout in India but is never farmed there.

In every Indian state, there are many varieties of *Cleome*. The biology, pharmacology, biochemistry, folklore, traditional medical uses, and several potential medical and therapeutic uses of the plant as determined by numerous laboratory studies and publications are all briefly reviewed in this article. This plant's therapeutic uses are also detailed in the Indian Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia and further ancient medical literature.

It is a key component of Narayana Churna in Ayurvedic therapy. It is used as an anthelmintic in Ayurveda for ear conditions, pruritis, and a number of other illnesses, including gastrointestinal infections and abnormalities of the gastrointestinal tract.

This is an effort to highlight the need for study and development while gathering and documenting data on many facets of *Cleome gynandra*.

Distribution

A ubiquitous and widely distributed herb in southern Africa, *cleome gynandra* grows in the Limpopo, the North-West, Gauteng, Namibia, the Northern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, the Free State, and Mpumalanga. Its semi-cultivated state, as in the Eastern Cape's Kentani District, has most likely increased its range.

It is most likely native to Africa and is currently found all over the world in tropical and subtropical areas. Native to tropical America, *C. hassleriana* is the cleome with the enormous pink or white flowers that is grown in flower gardens.

5.6 Morphological Characters

Morphology

It is an upright, annual herb that can grow to a height of 250–600 mm. It has many branches and can occasionally turn woody with age. The stem has longitudinal parallel lines and glandular hairs that make it sticky.

Leaves

The palmately complex leaves have three to five leaflets. The leaf stem has glandular hairs and is 20–50 mm long. The leaflets, which are 20–100 x 8–40 mm, smooth or glandular, taper toward the base, and radiate from the tip of the leaf stalk, are smooth to finely glandular on the underside and frequently have sporadic multicellular hairs on the major nerves.

Inflorescence

The bract is 3-foliolate to simple above, and the inflorescence is a terminal raceme with numerous flowers that elongates in fruit. smaller and sessile, but similar to the leaves.

Flowers

The flower stalk has glandular hairs and is 10–20 mm long. The white, occasionally rose pink, petals are 10–20 x 3-5 mm, are rounded at the apex, and then suddenly narrow to a basal claw. Bisexual, bracteate, white, or purple-tinged flowers.

Fruits

The fruits are packaged in capsules. The capsule is 30-150 x 2.5-5 mm, linear, sub-erect to

spreading, and has a persistent style of 2 mm. length, and the glandular, hairy valve has a thin texture. The brown seeds have a round shape, measure 1.5 mm in diameter, and have a surface that is hardly netted.

5.7 Microscopic Structures

Greasy and dark brown; under a microscope, many pieces of the testa's epidermis made up of polygonal, thin-walled cells are visible; clusters of reddish-brown, stone-like cells with non-lignified walls; many oval, spherical, or irregularly shaped protein bodies; lack of crystals and starch One The thickness of leaves varies between 112 and 398 μm .

Thick lamellar cuticle is present in the big, slightly deep, single-layered, tubular cells of the upper epidermis.

Both surfaces are covered in multiseriate glandular hairs, the foot has two to three cells buried in the epidermis, the stalk has two cells, and the big columnar About three to five tiers make up the head. Palisade and spongy parenchyma make up mesophyll; the former has adaxial hypodermal, single-layered, long, rectangular cells with few interstitial spaces and a lot of chloroplasts, while the latter has two to three layers with lots of intercellular spaces.

In principal veins, vascular bundles are big, arc-shaped, and collateral; in secondary veins, they are small and rounded. bundles of tertiary veins buried between mesophyll cells, xylem near the adaxial side, phloem toward the abaxial side, and big, distinct, barrel-shaped parenchymatous cells in the bundle sheath.

Massive, thick-walled, single-layered lower epidermis; massive, thick-walled, vertically oriented guard cells attached to thick-cuticle, lamellar subsidiary cells, creating minuscule outer ledges above guard cells.

Surface view of the epidermis shows that the costal epidermal cells are straight, thick-walled, rectangular to rhomboidal, and big, axially orientated five to ten times longer than broad.

Rarely found in the intercostal area are large, shaggy glandular hairs.

Stomata are found throughout the coastal and intercoastal regions. facing all directions, lying at the epidermis' level; medium in size, with a conspicuous sub-spherical or elliptical stomatal dimorphism; thickened at one or both poles.

The third type—anomocytic, anisocytic (Fig. 3), and tetracytic—is found more commonly than the other two. On both surfaces, these three stomata forms are prevalent. Seldom are stomatal anomalies, such as juxtaposed contiguous stomata, shriveled stomata, and abortive guard cells with thickened poles, 18.21 to 20.5 μm broad. The stomatal index was 20.9 μm on the adaxial side and 21.57 μm on the abaxial surface.

5.8 Phytochemical Constituent

From the seeds of *Cleome pentaphylla* Linn, oleic acid, linolic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid, arachidic acid, and a phytosterul were isolated (1937 by Ram Nath Misra and Sikhibhushan Dutt). The root contains two glyco-flavonones, namely Naringenin-4-galactoside-1 and Dihydrokaemferol-4f- galactoside-2 (Chauhan and et.al.).

The whole plant of *Cleome viscosa* was reported to contain a new glycoside-7, 3r-4-trihydroxyflavonone-5-0-a-Lrhamnopyranoside-3 by S.K. Srivastava and associates in 1979. Continuing their research, the same workers reported the isolation of a new glycoside, Naringenin.

The *Cleome* prenols that were separated from *Cleome spinosa* L. were reported by Takayuki Suga et al. They were determined to be decaprenol, nonaprenol, and undecaprenol, which is made up of three internal E-isoprene residues, one U-terminal isoprene, and the remaining Z-isoprene residues, in that order.

In 1979, S.B. Mahota and associates reported that *Cleome icosandra* Linn (syn *Cleome viscosa* Linn) had yielded a novel diterpene lactone called *Cleomeolide* -6. In 1980, S.K. Srivastava reported that a novel saponin known as stigma-5, 24-(28)-diene-3B-0-a-Lrhamnoside-7 had been isolated from *Cleome viscosa*.

In the same year, the same author also reported the isolation and identification of p-amyrin, lupeol, and a novel glycoside from *Cleome viscosa* roots.

5.9 PROPERTIES AND ACTION ACCORDING TO AYURVEDIC CONCEPT

Rasa : Katu

Guna : Laghu, Ruksa

Virya : Sita

Vipaka:Kattu

5.10 QUALITATIVE PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

The plant's nutritional value may vary with soil fertility, environment, plant type, plant age and the production techniques used.

NUTRITIONAL COMPOSITION

The seeds and leaves have a lot of nutrients like Carbohydrates, Protein, Fibres, Potassium, Calcium, Magnesium, etc.,

Table 4: Nutritional composition of 100g of leaves.

Constituents	Quantity Per 100g of Leaves Powder
BETA-CAROTENE	15.2
PROTEIN	410
FIBRE	1.3
CARBOHYDRATES	4.5
PHENOLIC	570
CALCIUM	212mg
PHOSPHORUS	12mg
ASH	2.1
IRON	15mg
SODIUM	33.6mg
MAGNESIUM	86mg
ZINC	0.76mg
COPPER	0.46
ASCORBIC	228
OXALATE	8.8
POTASSIUM	410
MOISTURE CONTENT	81.2

5.11 Medicinal uses

A decoction or infusion of boiled leaves and/or roots is administered to:

- Facilitate childbirth in pregnant women
- Treat stomach-ache and constipation
- Treat conjunctivitis
- Treat severe thread-worm infection
- Relieve chest pains.
- Arthritis is treated with the leaves.
- The leaves have anti-inflammatory properties.

The bruised leaves are rubefacient and vesicant, and are used to treat

- Headache,
- Neuralgia,
- Rheumatism and other localized pains.
- Diuretics.

They are rubbed on the affected Parts of the body, or applied as a poultice. Care must be taken to remove the application before it causes blisters, however.

In Taiwan *Cleome gynandra* is used to treat :

- Dysentery,
- Gonorrhoea,
- Malaria,
- Rheumatoid arthritis.

In India The plant had been traditionally used as an anthelmintic and rubefacient. Leaves are applied externally over the wounds to prevent the sepsis. The plant also used in the treatment of malaria, piles, Diuretics, rheumatism and in tumour. The decoction of the root is used to treat fevers.

6 MATERIALS AND METHOD

6.1 DRUGS AND REAGENTS

- Ethanolic Solvent
- Bromine Water
- Hydrochloric Acid
- Sodium Hydroxide
- Million's Reagent
- Meyer's Reagent
- Olive Oil
- Chloroform
- Sulfuric Acid
- Ferric Chloride
- Pyridine

- Sodium Nitroprusside
- Hydrochlorothiazide

6.2 INSTRUMENTS

- Soxhlet apparatus
- Diuretic cages
- Centrifuge
- Urine Analyser.

6.3 PLANT MATERIAL

In this present study, **Cleome gynandra plant** was selected because, It is considered for **Diuretic activity**, which means it may help to improve the Urine volume and used to treat renal-related disorders.

6.4 COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIAL

The fresh *Cleome gynandra* whole plant was collected from Karur, Tamilnadu. The plant was identified by a botanist (Dr.Jagatheesh kumar) from the Department of Botany, and he is a faculty of Sri Vijay Vidyalaya college of Arts and Science, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu.

6.5 PREPARATION OF THE ETHANOLIC PLANT EXTRACT:

Cleaning and Drying

Thoroughly clean the collected plant material to remove any dirt or debris. Allow it to air dry in a shaded area to prevent degradation of active compounds alternatively, you can use a food dehydrator or an oven set to a low temperature for drying.

Grinding or Crushing

Once the whole plant is dried, grind the plant material into a coarse powder using a mortar and pestle or an electric grinder. Ensure that the powder is uniform in texture to facilitate extraction.

Extraction

There are various methods for extracting bioactive compounds from plant material.

Common extraction methods include:

Ethanol Extraction

The solid powdered plant material is placed in the sox thimble, the ethanolic solvent was used for this extraction. The 80% of ethanolic solvent was placed in the round bottom flask and the solvent is heated under the reflux by using heating mantle under the controlled temperature. Seal the container and let it soak for a specified period, with occasional shaking or stirring. After extraction, filter the mixture to remove solid particles, and then evaporate the ethanol under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator or by air-drying to obtain the crude extract.

Concentration and Drying

Once the extraction is complete, concentrate the extract by using a rotary evaporator or by air-drying. The resulting concentrated extract was there stored in a cool, dry place for further use.

Quality Control

Performed appropriate quality control tests to assess the phytochemical composition, purity, quality, and potency of the extract. This include assays for specific bioactive compounds, such as Saponins, Tannin, flavonoids, Terpenoids, Cardiac glycosides, alkaloids, or phenolic compounds, as well as tests for contaminants.

Standardization

Standardized the extract to ensure consistency in its composition and therapeutic effects. This involved adjusting the extraction parameters or adding standardized markers for quantification. It is important to note that the specific extraction method and conditions vary depending on the desired phytochemicals and the intended use of the extract. Additionally, I ensured compliance with ethical and legal guidelines regarding the collection and use of plant materials.

Yield and color determination

The color of the extract was observed visually. The yield of the extract was calculated using the following formula:

$$\% \text{ yield} = (\text{Weight of the extract} / \text{Weight of powder taken}) \times 10$$

6.6 QUALITATIVE PHYTO CHEMICAL SCREENING

Tannins, alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, phenolic compounds, proteins, Vitamins, calcium, Magnesium were screened on the leaf extract.

Test for tannin

The tannins were screened using the protocol as stated by Amadi *et al.* An equivalent amount of bromine water was combined with two milliliters (2 mL) of the extract. The development of reddish green precipitates was interpreted as an indication that tannins were present.

Test for alkaloids

The screening procedure for alkaloids followed the guidelines provided by Amadi *et al.* After being mixed with five milliliters of 2% hydrochloric acid in a steam bath, one milliliter of extract was filtered. Meyer's reagent was then applied to the filtrate. A precipitate with a cream color was considered a positive alkaloids result.

Test for flavonoids

The flavonoid screening procedure followed Amadi *et al.* instructions. The extract was combined with an equal amount of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in one milliliter (one mL) and thoroughly agitated. Precipitate formation was interpreted as a favorable flavonoid outcome.

Test for phlobatannins

The phytochemical screening of phlobatannins was conducted using the protocol as outlined by Amadi *et al.* When five milliliters (5 mL) of the extract were mixed with two milliliters (0.5 mL) of 1% hydrochloric acid (HCl), red precipitate was produced, which indicated the presence of phytobannins.

Test for proteins

After combining four milliliters of the extract with five milliliters of distilled water, the mixture was left for three hours before being brought to a boil. After that, 02 mL of the boiling extract and 01 mL of Million's reagent were combined and forcefully shaken. A pinkish precipitate was interpreted as a protein test result.

Test for saponin

The saponins were screened using the procedure outlined by Amadi *et al.* One milliliter of the extract was combined with two drops of olive oil, then thoroughly shaken. The emulsion's development was interpreted as a sign that saponins were working.

Test for phenolic compound

The phenol glucinol test was applied Two milliliters of the extract were mixed with one percent FeCl₃, and the presence of any blue, violet, purple, green, or reddish-brown color

was considered a favorable indicator of the existence of phenolic chemicals.

Test for Terpenoids

In a test tube containing 10 mL of methanol, one gram of seed sample was agitated before being filtered. Following that, 5mL of extract, 2mL of chloroform, and 3 mL of sulfuric acid were added. The presence of Terpenoids in the chosen plants is shown by the formation of a reddish brown tint.

Cardiac glycosides

1.0 mL of pyridine was used to dissolve a half-gram of the material. Three drops of 20% NaOH and five drops of 2% sodium nitroprusside were added. For cardiac glycosides, the presence of a deep red color that fades to brown yellow was interpreted as a positive result.

6.7 EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL

The animals used for this study were both male and female wistar albino rats with average weight of 150-200g. They were housed in polypropylene cages under standard environmental conditions, including a 12-hour light/dark cycle, a temperature of $25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, and humidity ranging from 35% to 60% and adequate air ventilation is provided to the rats.

The rats were given the standard pellet diet from (Nutrivet Life Sciences, pune Maharashtra, India) and fresh water.

They were allowed to acclimatize to then environment under optimum feeds(Standard Commercial Diet) with full access to drinking water for a period of 3 weeks prior to the commencement of the experiment.

6.8 APPROVAL OF PROTOCOL

The experimental procedures were conducted according to the guidelines prescribed by the Animal Welfare Board and received prior approval from the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Sri vijay vidyalaya college of pharmacy, Nallampalli, Dharmapuri. The IAEC is constituted under the Committee for Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA), Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India (Registration No.146/PO/Re/A/11/CPCSEA. All experimental protocols adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring the welfare and human treatment of the animals throughout the study.

6.9 ACUTE TOXICITY STUDIES

To establish safety level the acute toxicity studies were carried out in accordance with OECD – 423 guidelines.

Cleome gynandra plant extract were used in acute toxicology tests on albino wistar rats. Before the trial began, the weight of each rats were recorded after an over night fast. Four set of two animals each were created: 100mg/kg, 500mg/kg, 1500 mg/kg, 2000mg/kg. The animals were regularly monitored for changes in symptoms, signs, and mortality.

6.10 BODY WEIGHT OF RATS

Initial and final body weights of the animals were recorded at the end of the treatments period (4weeks) and the weight of the albino rat were monitored every day through the period of the experiment. Finally the urine sample was collected to analyses.

6.11 SCREENING OF DIURETIC ACTIVITY

Experimental methods

Diuretic activity was assessed by Metabolic cage and Urine Analyzer.

Experimental design

The experimental design is involved the use of both male and female albino wistar rats weighing between 150 – 250g. A total of 24 rats were divided into 4 groups, with each group consisting of 6 rats.

The groups were designated as follows:

- **Group A (normal control):** Rats in this group received the normal feed .
- **Group B (Hydrochlorothiazide):** Rats in this group received Hydrochlorothiazide 12.5mg/kg.of body weight.
- **Group C (Test-1, 100mg/kg):** Rats in this group received test compound ethanolic extract of Cleome gynandra at a dose of (100 mg/kg b.w) administered orally.
- **Group D (Test-2, 250mg/kg):** Rats in this group received test compound ethanolic extract of Cleome gynandra at a dose of (250 mg/kg b.w) administered orally.

PROCEDURE

The rats were divided into 4 groups and named as **Group A, Group B, Group C, Group D**, with each group consisting of 6 rats.

In Group A Rats are Received The Normal Standard Pellet Diet and Adequate Water, Group B considered as a standard drug (Hydrochlorothiazide) at dose of 12.5mg/kg. Group C considered as Test-1, (100 mg/kg) this group of Rats received test compound ethanolic extract of Cleome gynandra at a dose of (100 mg/kg b.w) administered orally. Group D considered as Test-2 (250mg/kg) In this group of rats received test compound ethanolic extract of Cleome gynandra at a dose of (250 mg/kg b.w) administered orally.

6.12 URINE SAMPLE COLLECTED

Urine samples were collected from the rats Using Lipschitz model. After 5 hrs of the Administration of feed and drug the urine sample was collected and measured using the metabolic cage. Put the animal in a metabolic cage and return it to its home cage When it urinates.

6.13 DETERMINATION OF URINE VOLUME BY USING METABOLIC CAGE

The urine volume was measured by metabolic cage thereby to found that diuretic activity of the plant extract.

METABOLIC CAGE.

PROCEDURE

The diuretic activity was evaluated by Lipschitz model. In this model Wistar albino rats weighing 150-200g are used. The animals were fasted and deprived of food and water for 20hrs prior to the experiment. On the day of experiment, the Group I animals serving as negative control, received Normal saline (25ml/kg) per orally, the Group II serving as positive control animals received Hydrochlorothiazide 12.5mg/kg body weight per orally,

Group III received 100mg/kg ethanolic extract of *Cleome gynandra* orally and Group IV received 250mg/kg ethanolic extract of *Cleome gynandra* orally.

Immediately after the administration the animals were kept in diuretic cages (3 per cage) specially designed to separate urine and fecal matter and kept at room temperature of $25 \pm 0.5^\circ \text{C}$ throughout the experiment.

The total volume of urine was collected at the end of 5hrs after dosing. During this period no water and food was made available to animals. The urine volume was measured and will be expressed in ml/5hrs. The concentrations of the electrolytes Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- , in urine will be expressed in terms of mmol/L. Diuretic index and diuretic activity will be calculated as,

Diuretic index = $\frac{\text{Urinary excretion of treated group}}{\text{Urinary excretion of control group}}$

Diuretic activity = $\frac{\text{Diuretic action of test drug}}{\text{Diuretic action of standard drug}}$

Diuretic action of standard drug

Saliuretic index = $\frac{\text{Concentration of electrolytes in urine of test group}}{\text{Concentration of electrolytes in urine of control}}$

6.13 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The results was analyzed by calculating the Mean and Standard Deviation. For multiple group comparison one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Post-hoc Scheffe' test for statistical significance between groups. The values was compared at 0.05 level of significance. $P < 0.05$ was considered as significant. All the results were analyzed by IBM SPSS statistics ©IBM Corporation and Other(s) 1989, 2012 software was used for statistical analysis purpose.

6.14 DETERMINATION OF ELECTROLYTES ACTIVITY

The **Urine analyzer** determines the Electrolytes activity

CENTRIFUGE.

The **Urine Analyzer** can measure Na^+ , K^+ , Cl^- Electrolytes.

Determining Electrolytes Concentration using a Electrolyte analyser involves several steps:

1. **Sample Collection:** Collect a Urine sample from the rats using appropriate procedures
2. **Sample Preparation:** The Urine sample needs to be centrifuged to separate the electrolytes.
3. **Loading the Analyzer:** Place the prepared sample into the sample chamber of the Electrolyte analyzer according to the manufacturer's instructions.
4. **Analysis:** Initiate the analysis process on the Electrolyte analyzer. The analyzer will use its internal mechanisms to measure the Electrolyte concentration in the Urine sample.
5. **Interpretation of Results:** Once the analysis is complete, the Electrolyte analyzer will display the Electrolytes concentration of sodium, potassium, chloride in the sample.
6. **Quality Control:** Perform regular quality control checks on the analyzer to ensure accuracy and reliability of results. This may involve running control samples of known Electrolytes concentrations to verify the performance of the analyzer.
7. **Record Keeping:** Record the Electrolytes concentrations results accurately in the medical records for future reference and comparison.

7 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Phytochemical evaluation

Table 5: Phytochemical Evaluation of Cleome gynandra Plant.

Phytochemical	Status
Tannins	++
Alkoloids	+
Flavonoids	+
Steroids	+
Phlobatannins	-
Proteins	+
Saponins	++
Phenoliccompound	+
Terpenoids	-
Cardiacglycosides	-

+ = **Present in low concentration**

++ = **Present in high concentration**

- = **Absent**

Tannins, phlobatannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, steroids, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, phenolic compounds, proteins, are among the phytochemicals examined in the current study. While the amounts of proteins steroids, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds were low, the concentrations of tannins and saponins were significant.

In the leaf extract of Cleome gynandra, phenolphthaleins, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, are present in small amount. Various writers have reported on the physiological effects and phytoactivity of some of these phytochemicals. It has been observed that tannins have analgesic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing effects.

It is well known that saponins have an unpleasant taste and have a frothy consistency and diuretic property. It has been reported that saponins have antibacterial effects. It has been observed that dietary flavonoids prevent coronary heart disease. Alkaloids have a reductive effect on headache and fever.

They also have antimicrobial and analgesic qualities. Steroids are engaged as precursors to these hormones and form the nucleus of all steroid hormones. Several publications have reported that the majority of phenolic compounds have insecticidal properties. It has been documented that proteins play a part in energy production and body building. Additionally,

proteins act as a precursor to the growth of microbes. They are helpful to the pulp, textile, and dye industries as well.

7.2 Evaluation of acute toxicity studies of *amaranthus viridis*

Cleome gynandra plant extract used in treatment of Diuretics.

Acute oral toxicity study for extract in albino wistar rats was carried out to evaluate the maximum safe dose of Cleome gynandra plant extract. The acute toxicity testing revealed no death upto doses of 2000mg/kg.

Table 6: Acute Toxicity Study of Cleome gynandra Plant Extract.

Group	Dose	Route of administration	Death
1	100mg	Oral	0
2	500mg	Oral	0
3	1500mg	Oral	0
4	2000mg	Oral	0

Chart 1: Acute Toxicity Study of Cleome gynandra Plant Extract.

7.3 Evaluation of diuretic activity in cleome gynandra plant

Table 7: The Effect of Cleome gynandra plant extract of Diuretic activity.

Drug Treated	Urine volume	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Cl ⁻
Group - A Negative control	2.34 ± 0.11	145.31 ± 3.21	57.16 ± 3.32	20 ± 3.71
Group-B Positive control (std.drug)	20.95 ± 0.22	171 ± 4.54	67.2 ± 2.45	45 ± 2.17
Group-C Test - 1 (100mg/kg)	14.21 ± 1.28	158 ± 2.45	70.95 ± 3.33	55 ± 2.12
Group-D Test - 2 (250mg/kg)	13.85 ± 0.51	159.95 ± 3.82	81.23 ± 2.32	51.76 ± 2.12

Chart 2: Evaluation of diuretic activity of Cleome gynandra Plant Extract.

7.4 Evaluation of Saliuretic Index

Table 8: Evaluation of sali uretic Index.

Treated group	Na+	K+
Negative control	-	-
Positive control	2.32	2.19
Test drug - 1(100mg/kg)	1.38	2.18
Test drug - 2(250mg/kg)	2.11	1.17

Chart 3: Evaluation of Saliuretic Index.

7.5 Showing the diuretic index and diuretic activity of various groups.

Table 9: Diuretic index and Diuretic activity.

Group	Diuretic index	Diuretic Activity
Negative Control	-	-
Positive Control	9.54	-
Test Drug -1(100mg)	5.23	0.52
Test Drug -2(250mg)	6.11	0.58

Chart 4: Diuretic index and Diuretic activity.

DISCUSSION

If the standard drug Hydrochlorothiazide shows increase volume of urine and electrolytes level. The test -1 Drug Plant Extract (100mg/kg) shows low increase volume of urine and electrolytes.

The test -2 Drug Plant Extract (250mg/kg) shows increased volume of urine & electrolytes near to Hydrochlorothiazide but not equal and higher than Hydrochlorothiazide.

Therefore the test -1 Drug produced almost 50% activity when compared to test -2 Drug and Hydrochlorothiazide and that test -2 Drug produced almost 90% of activity when compared to Hydrochlorothiazide.

8. CONCLUSION

The results of The present study indicates that ethanolic extract of Cleome gynandra is a potential diuretic. However further studies are required to separate the phyto constituents responsible for the diuretic activity and to confirm the safe use in renal disorders.

A significant Diuretic property of plant extract of *Cleome gynandra* in experimental rats. In conclusion, the results of this study suggest that **Test Extract-1 And Test Extract- 2** of *Cleome gynandra* could be used in the Diuretic activity when consumed because of its phytochemical constituents and diuretics boosting properties.

It suggest that the ethanolic plant extract of *Cleome gynandra* is relatively safe and possesses a significant Diuretic property; therefore, it may be a potential lead in the discovery of drug for treatment of Diuretic.

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